

Dynamic fracture analysis in quasi-brittle materials via a finite element approach based on the combination of the ALE formulation and M-integral method.

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ABSTRACT

This work proposes an efficient modeling approach to reproduce dynamic crack propagation phenomena in quasi-brittle materials. The proposed strategy enhances the capabilities of a standard FE model using the Moving Mesh (MM) technique and the M-integral method. The MM serves to handle the changes in the geometry caused by the crack growth. In particular, the method adopts the Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation, which enables moving the mesh nodes according to the crack path, avoiding the recourse to continuous remeshing actions. In this context, the M-integral extracts Dynamic Stress Intensity Factors (DSIFs) at the crack front. Specifically, the ALE formulation of the M-integral is implemented, which enables computing DSIFs during the mesh movement without losing accuracy. The validity of the proposed method has been assessed through comparisons with experimental and numerical data reported in the literature. The results show that the proposed method represents a reliable tool for simulating crack propagation mechanisms.

KEYWORDS: Crack propagation; ALE; Moving mesh technique; Finite element method; Interaction integral

1 Introduction

Quasi-brittle materials (*e.g.*, ceramic, concrete, glass fiber composites) are part of various key components frequently employed in civil engineering structures and mechanics systems. Such materials possess excellent thermal properties, incredible durability, and high resistance against aggressive natural agents. However, they are highly vulnerable to mechanical actions induced by dynamic loadings (*e.g.*, wind forces, seismic-induced vibrations, and impact by foreign objects). Indeed, under dynamic loadings, the pre-existing and unavoidable material defects expand via dangerous dynamic crack propagation mechanisms, thus compromising the overall material integrity.

The process of crack initiation and propagation in quasi-brittle materials under dynamic conditions is more complex than what occurs in quasi-static circumstances [1-3]. Indeed, under dynamic conditions, a pre-existing material defect advances unstably according to jerky movements, involving sequences of crack initiation, fast propagation, and crack arrest events. In this context, inertia effects are significant, especially when the load changes abruptly, thus influencing the fracture behavior. Further, material properties become rate-dependent for high loading rates. Finally, stress waves originate and spread across the material under suddenly applied dynamic loadings, thus notably influencing the stress and strain fields near the crack tip region [4].

Therefore, to assess the integrity of quasi-brittle materials under dynamic loadings, it is essential using proper analysis strategies able to account for all the above complexities and, further, capable of providing comprehensive information regarding (*i*) crack initiation conditions, (*ii*) the direction of crack propagation, and (*iii*) the velocity of dynamically advancing crack fronts. However, developing accurate and highly

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efficient analysis approaches for investigating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle material has never been a trivial task.

The first approaches developed in the framework of dynamic fracture mechanics have been analytic [1, 4-6]. These approaches have provided analytical solutions for dynamic fracture problems with relatively simple geometries and loading conditions. Despite their utility, such analytical formulations are not applicable in practice because real applications typically involve articulated geometries and complex loading configurations. In such circumstances, numerical simulations are undoubtedly more suitable as a means of analysis. To date, various numerical strategies exist for simulating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms occurring in quasi-brittle materials. In computational fracture mechanics, it has become commonplace to categorize numerical approaches in mesh-based and meshless methods [7-10].

Meshless methods (*e.g.*, element-free Galerkin method [11], the cracking particles method (CPM) [12], and the particle difference method [13]) configure the computational domain as a scattered set of nodal points, providing additional information regarding external boundaries and internal crack surfaces [14]. Dynamic crack propagation mechanisms are simulated by simply extending the pre-defined internal cracks according to the conditions dictated by fracture criteria. Although meshless methods permit reproducing arbitrarily growing cracks with incredible versatility, the accuracy of numerical solutions strictly depends on the number of computational nodes used. Indeed, acceptable solutions need highly refined computational domains (*i.e.*, dense points clouds). This requirement makes meshless methods computationally expensive, thus limiting their operative range to simple and relatively small geometries.

Conversely, mesh-based methods discretize the computational domain in several finite elements of various geometric shapes, thus forming a computational mesh. Among the mesh-based methods, the most widely used for simulating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle materials is the Finite Element Method (FEM) because of its simplicity and efficiency in modeling articulated geometries [15-20].

Early FEM models used simple nodal release techniques to reproduce the crack propagation mechanisms [17, 18]. Despite its simplicity, such a strategy involved significant mesh dependency issues. In fact, consistent with the fundamentals of nodal release techniques, a pre-existing crack can grow only along the boundaries of the pre-assigned computational mesh. This drawback leads to a considerable loss of accuracy in numerical solutions, especially regarding the prediction of crack trajectories.

To address such unpleasant mesh dependency issues, recent FEM models have adopted special remeshing techniques [17, 21], which update the computational mesh during each step of the crack advance consistently with the development of the crack trajectory [16, 22]. However, tracing random growing cracks needs continuous updating of the computational mesh. Such a circumstance increases the computational time required to perform numerical simulations. Moreover, the transition from old to new mesh configurations may lead to loss of accuracy issues, thus compromising the reliability of the numerical solution. These drawbacks make traditional FE methods somewhat inconvenient for analyzing dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle materials.

As an alternative to classic FE approaches, enhanced FEM methodologies based on either advanced finite element formulations or cohesive zone models [23-28] have been proposed. In particular, the first group comprises all numerical approaches developed in the framework of the Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) [29-32]. XFEM-based methods correctly simulate the initiation and propagation of arbitrary growing cracks using fixed computational meshes (*i.e.*, without requiring re-meshing actions). To enable this representation, finite element formulations are enhanced by discontinuous displacement fields, defined through enriched shape functions. However, the use of enriched shape functions inevitably adds extra degrees of freedom to the governing equations of the problem. This aspect may cause numerical difficulties when multiple cracks originate and propagate as frequently occur in quasi-brittle materials (*e.g.*, crack branching). In addition, handling random growing cracks requires very refined meshes, thus involving considerable computational resources to perform numerical simulations. Such an inconvenience implies that X-FEM procedures may be unpracticable with larger and articulated geometries.

Recent advances in computational fracture mechanics have given rise to hybrid methodologies, which combine the advantages of traditional approaches while minimizing their drawbacks as far as possible. Such hybrid approaches are attractive because they provide reliable predictions of dynamic crack propagation mechanisms meanwhile ensuring optimal computational performances.

One of the most prominent hybrid approaches proposed in the last years is the Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method (SB-FEM) developed by Ooi et al. [33]. The SB-FEM combines the flexibility of the FEM in handling complex geometric configurations and the computational efficiency of the Boundary Element Method (BEM) to manage remeshing actions.

Further hybrid methodologies have risen by enhancing traditional methods' capabilities through advancing numerical procedures, such as, for instance, those developed into the framework of Moving Mesh (MM) techniques [34, 35]. The MM is a powerful numerical technique that permits moving the nodes of the computational domain as a function of some parameter, which either or not can be part of the problem under investigation. Therefore, a new mesh need not be generated for each domain configuration since the position of mesh nodes changes consistently with geometry variations. In such a context, using the Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) formulation allows relocating the mesh nodes with great regularity and low computational honors. More interestingly, concerning mesh-based approaches, the ALE formulation alleviates finite elements distortions induced by mesh node movements [36, 37], thus reducing considerably the overall amount of remeshing actions required to perform numerical simulations.

The possibility of continuously adapting the computational mesh to the evolution of the geometry domain because of advancing cracks makes the ALE formulation an attractive strategy for simulating dynamic crack propagation processes in quasi-brittle materials. Indeed, dynamic fracture mechanisms often involve randomly growing cracks running at high velocities, which imply rapid evolutions of the geometry domain. Reproducing such fracture behaviors requires flexible and computationally efficient numerical methods.

Regardless of the numerical method adopted for simulating crack propagation phenomena in quasi-brittle material, a key aspect of all numerical approaches is the evaluation of fracture variables at the crack front,

specifically the Dynamic Stress Intensity Factors (DSIFs). DSIFs are fundamental variables typically used in fracture mechanics criteria [38, 39] to define the condition of crack initiation, the direction of crack propagation, and the crack tip velocity. Therefore, a proper evaluation of the DSIFs is essential to gain reliable predictions of dynamic propagation processes. Among the various approaches adopted to evaluate the DSIFs, one of the most used is the Interaction Integral method (also known as the M -integral method), initially proposed by Yau et al. [40], because of its simplicity and accuracy.

Note that the accuracy of the M -integral method strictly depends on the arrangement of computational mesh in the region around the crack tip. Usually, refined and regular-arranged computational meshes are mandatory for avoiding loss of accuracy issues in the numerical integration procedures employed in M -integral computation. However, this requirement represents a considerable inconvenience for standard FE procedures used for simulating crack propagation phenomena. Indeed, ensuring regular computational meshes during each step of the propagation process leads to continuous remeshing actions, thereby increasing computational burdens notably. Therefore, using the M -integral in traditional FE approaches could be prohibitive for simulating dynamic fracture propagation phenomena unless adopting suitable strategies to circumvent the requirement for regular mesh arrangements.

Recently, the authors of the present paper have developed an efficient FE-based approach that combines the ALE formulation and the M -integral method to simulate crack propagation phenomena occurring in homogeneous and heterogeneous quasi-brittle materials under thermo-mechanical loadings (see [41, 42]). In particular, this approach implements the ALE formulation of the M -integral, which represents a worthy expedient to circumvent the requirement for regular-arranged mesh around the crack tip region. This is motivated by the fact that the ALE formulation of the M -integral allows performing numerical integrations directly over deforming elements (because of the motion of mesh nodes) without losing accuracy. Besides, the possibility of continuously extracting fracture variables at the crack front permits instantaneous evaluation of the propagation direction, thereby allowing the tracing of smooth crack trajectories.

However, the approach presented in [41, 42] has only been used to reproduce fracture propagation mechanisms under quasi-static conditions. Therefore, its applicability to the simulation of dynamic crack propagation phenomena in quasi-brittle materials requires further development.

The primary aim of this paper is to develop an FE-based numerical approach based on the combination of the ALE formulation and the M -integral method for simulating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle materials.

Starting from the modeling approach presented by the authors in [41, 42], the present work introduces the following key novelties:

- Re-stating the fundamental equations of solids and fracture mechanics in a dynamic context through the ALE formulation.
- Implementing the ALE formulation of M -integral for extracting Dynamic Stress Intensity Factors (DSIFs) at the crack front.

- Introducing proper fracture criteria to manage numerically crack initiation conditions, rapid crack propagation mechanisms, and crack arrest events.

The remaining part of the paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 deals with the theoretical background of the proposed modeling approach. Section 3 treats numerical implementation aspects, describing the computational procedure used by the proposed approach for managing the propagation process. Section 4 reports numerical results to assess the accuracy and reliability of the proposed method. In particular, comparison results between analytic, experimental, and numerical data reported in the literature are proposed to support the discussion. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of the works.

2 Theoretical background

This section reports the leading theoretical concepts used to define the modeling strategy presented in the current paper. It comprises four sub-sections: Section 2.1 provides the fundamental equations of the ALE formulation. Section 2.2 reports the governing equations of solid mechanics and the moving mesh problem. Section 2.3 begins with an overview of the M -integral formulation typically used to analyze dynamic fracture problems. dynamic fracture problems. Then it continues with the definition of the ALE formulation of the M -integral method. Finally, Section 2.4 summarizes the fracture criteria and governing laws employed to define crack initiation conditions, the direction of crack propagation, and crack tip velocity.

2.1 Basics of the Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation

Traditional problems of continuum mechanics are formulated either in a spatial or a material system of coordinates, denoted as R_x and R_X , respectively. Spatial coordinate axes are fixed in space, and spatial coordinates (\mathbf{x}) identify the spatial positions occupied by the material particles of the continuum over time. Conversely, material coordinate axes are fixed to the continuum in its reference configuration (usually the domain configuration at time $t=0$) and follow the continuum as it deforms. In the material coordinate system, the coordinate \mathbf{X} identifies each material particle of the continuum. Specifically, R_x varies according to the continuum motion, while \mathbf{X} remains the same. At time $t=0$, spatial and material coordinates of a particle coincide, whereas they differ for $t>0$. Physics problems formulated using material coordinates are generally defined as Lagrangian approaches, whereas spatial formulations characterize Eulerian approaches.

In numerical methods devoted to analyzing continuum mechanics, Lagrangian approaches fix the mesh grid to the continuum. Hence, the finite element mesh follows the material continuum while deforms and changes position. The fact that each finite element comprises identical material particles provides a significant advantage in computational problems that analyze the behavior of free surfaces or interfaces between different materials. However, when large material deformations affect the continuum, the finite elements of the computational mesh undergo excessive distortions, thus causing loss of accuracy and computational instability issues in numerical simulations.

On the other hand, Eulerian approaches adopt a fixed mesh and analyze the behavior of the continuum while it passes through the computational grid. For this reason, Eulerian approaches are more suitable than

Lagrangian ones for analyzing the behavior of continua affected by considerable distortions (*e.g.*, fluids). However, their weakness relies on the impossibility of accurately tracking the behavior of free surfaces or interfaces between different materials.

The ALE formulation has emerged as an ingenious strategy that combines the strengths of the Lagrangian and Eulerian approaches while reducing their weakness as far as possible. In the ALE approaches, the governing equations of the continuum mechanics are formulated regarding a third coordinate system, that is, the mesh (or referential) coordinates system R_χ , in which the coordinate χ identifies the nodes of the computational mesh. Besides, referential and spatial coordinates coincide at $t=0$.

The referential system R_χ has twofold fundamental properties: First, it can move liberally into the space according to specific conditions that can be not related to the mechanics of the problem under investigation; Second, it can move independently from material particles (*i.e.*, R_χ can differ from R_X).

The modeling approach defined in the present paper adopts the ALE formulation for tracing the geometry evolution of the computational domain caused by the growth of internal defects (*i.e.*, the advance of internal surfaces). Therefore, the mesh nodes change their position during the numerical simulation according to the conditions dictated by classic fracture mechanics criteria concerning crack onset circumstances, crack propagation direction, and crack tip velocity.

Fig. 1 shows a schematic describing the use of the ALE formulation in the proposed modeling strategy for simulating dynamic crack propagation phenomena in quasi-brittle materials. It depicts the configurations assumed by a pre-cracked continuum material at an initial time t_0 (*i.e.*, a reference configuration) and a subsequent instant \bar{t} (*i.e.*, the current configuration), respectively. In particular, the internal defect grows by passing from the reference to the current configuration, and the computational mesh adapts accordingly. The figure highlights the position of some material particles and mesh nodes. Consistent with the ALE formulation, material particles move differently from mesh nodes. Note that the figure also illustrates the current configurations regarding material and referential domains separately, thus clearly depicting all domain frames involved.

The links between the referential (R_χ), materials (R_X), and spatial (R_x) domains are time-dependent and bijective mapping functions. In particular, the mapping function between the material and spatial domains is an application $\varphi(\mathbf{X}, t)$, which describes the motion of material particles in space. Similarly, the referential and spatial domain are linked through an application $\Phi(\chi, t)$ that describes the motion of the nodes of the computational mesh in space. Besides, the mapping function between the referential and material domains is an application $\Psi(\chi, t)$.

Fig. 1. The Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation: Relationships between Spatial (R_x), Material (R_χ), and Referential (R_χ) frames

Such mapping functions are defined, respectively, as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi} : R_x \times [t_0, t[\rightarrow R_x \times [t_0, t[\mid (\mathbf{X}, t) \mapsto \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{X}, t) = (\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (1)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Phi} : R_\chi \times [t_0, t[\rightarrow R_x \times [t_0, t[\mid (\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) \mapsto \boldsymbol{\Phi}(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) = (\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (2)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi} : R_\chi \times [t_0, t[\rightarrow R_x \times [t_0, t[\mid (\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) \mapsto \boldsymbol{\Psi}(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) = (\mathbf{X}, t) \quad (3)$$

From a computational point of view, the use of the ALE formulation requires that the governing equations of solid and fracture mechanics, traditionally formulated in the material domain (R_χ), must be restated regarding the referential domain (R_χ). To this end, it is necessary relating the gradient and time derivatives of vectorial fields in material and referential domains.

Let a generic time-dependent vectorial field be described by $\mathbf{v}^M(\mathbf{X}, t)$ and $\mathbf{v}^R(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t)$, in the material and referential systems, respectively. Apexes M and R denote that the forms of the vectorial fields are, in general, different with reference to the material (M) and referential (R) domains. According to the ALE formulation, the gradient of $\mathbf{v}^M(\mathbf{X}, t)$ in the material domain can be expressed in the referential coordinates by performing spatial differencing of $\mathbf{v}^M(\mathbf{X}, t) = \mathbf{v}^R[\boldsymbol{\Psi}(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t), t]$, *i.e.*:

$$\nabla^M \mathbf{v}^M = \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}^M}{\partial \mathbf{X}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}^R}{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\Psi}} = \nabla^R \mathbf{v}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \quad (4)$$

Being $\nabla^M(\cdot) = \partial(\cdot)/\partial \mathbf{X}$, $\nabla^R(\cdot) = \partial(\cdot)/\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}$, and \mathbf{J}_Ψ the Jacobian matrix of the mapping function $\boldsymbol{\Psi}(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t)$ defined as:

$$\mathbf{J}_\Psi = \frac{\partial \Psi(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}} \quad (5)$$

Noting that the bijection condition of Ψ guarantees that, at every time, it exists a one-to-one relation between the material and the referential configurations. From a mathematical point of view, this condition implies that the determinant of \mathbf{J}_Ψ is a positive number.

Let the material and referential time derivatives of $\mathbf{v}^M(\mathbf{X}, t)$ and $\mathbf{v}^R(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t)$ be expressed, respectively, as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}^M = \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}^M(\mathbf{X}, t) \right|_{\mathbf{X}} \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}^R = \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}^R(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) \right|_{\boldsymbol{\chi}} \quad (7)$$

These time derivatives are related by the chain rule, *i.e.*:

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}^R(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) \right|_{\boldsymbol{\chi}} = \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}^M(\mathbf{X}, t) \right|_{\mathbf{X}} + \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}^M}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}}{\partial t} \right|_{\boldsymbol{\chi}} \rightarrow \dot{\mathbf{v}}^R = \dot{\mathbf{v}}^M + \nabla^M \mathbf{v}^M \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \quad (8)$$

Where $\dot{\mathbf{X}}^R$ is a convective term denoting the velocity of the mesh in the material domain. It is worth noting that this term has little significance from a physical point of view. As a matter of fact, it has only computational importance because numerical solvers compute and store in the solution vector referential time derivative only. Introducing Eq. (4) into Eq. (8), the material time derivative can be expressed into referential coordinates as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}^M = \dot{\mathbf{v}}^R - \nabla^R \mathbf{v}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \quad (9)$$

The relationships between the second time derivatives regarding material and referential frames can be computed applying Eq. (9) recursively, thus obtaining

$$\ddot{\mathbf{v}}^M = \ddot{\mathbf{v}}^R - 2\nabla^R \dot{\mathbf{v}}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R - \nabla^R \mathbf{v}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \ddot{\mathbf{X}}^R + \nabla^R \left[\nabla^R \mathbf{v}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \right] \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R + \nabla^R \mathbf{v}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \nabla^R \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \quad (10)$$

Finally, using the ALE formulation requires proper mesh-displacement prescriptions governing the motion of mesh nodes, *i.e.*, a suitable form for $\Phi(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t)$ describing the motion in space. This further aspect will be investigated in detail in the next paragraph.

2.2 Governing equations

The modeling approach proposed in the present paper comprises two sets of governing equations: the first set deals with the fundamental equations of solid mechanics that describe the mechanical behavior of the material component under investigation. The second set of equations governs the motion of the referential domain, *i.e.*, the nodes of the computational mesh.

The fundamental equations of solid mechanics are defined with reference to a 2D homogeneous body whose external boundary $\partial\Omega$ is assumed to be Lipschitz-continuous. In particular, we assume that $\partial\Omega$ consists of two portions, indicated by $\partial\Omega_u$ and $\partial\Omega_p$, such that $\partial\Omega = \partial\Omega_u + \partial\Omega_p$, where Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions act, respectively (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. A two-dimensional body affected by a dynamically growing crack

The body presents an internal crack, denoted by $\partial\Omega_c$, that departs from the external boundary and culminates to a crack tip (O_c). Such a tip serves as the origin of a local coordinate system, whose horizontal axis is parallel to the inner extremity of the internal crack faces.

The crack grows dynamically at a velocity $\dot{a}(t)$ (variable in time) along the propagation direction identified by the unit vector \mathbf{n}_c , inclined of $\theta_c(t)$ regarding the crack tip local coordinate system.

Under the hypotheses of small displacements and absence of interaction forces between the crack faces along $\partial\Omega_c$, the mechanic behavior of the body is governed by the following weak form:

$$h \int_{\Omega} [\mathbf{C} : \nabla \mathbf{u}] \nabla \delta \mathbf{u} d\Omega - h \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \delta \mathbf{u} d\Omega - h \int_{\partial\Omega_p} \mathbf{p} \delta \mathbf{u} dS = -h \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \delta \mathbf{u} d\Omega \quad (11)$$

being \mathbf{C} the fourth-order constitutive tensor, h the body thickness, \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{p} the body force and surface traction vectors, respectively, and ρ the mass density. Further, \mathbf{u} and $\delta \mathbf{u}$ represent the displacement field and a suitable set of virtual displacements defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \left\{ \mathbf{u} \in H^1(\Omega) \mid \mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \text{ on } \partial\Omega_u \right\} \\ \delta \mathbf{u} &= \left\{ \delta \mathbf{u} \in H^1(\Omega) \mid \delta \mathbf{u} = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega_u \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where H^1 denotes the Sobolev space and $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ the vector containing prescribed displacements on $\partial\Omega_u$.

Eq. (11) represents the dynamic equilibrium equation of the body in the material configuration (*i.e.*, R_X). The ALE formulation of Eq. (11), which expresses the dynamic equilibrium of the body concerning the referential domain (*i.e.*, R_X), can be obtained by expressing gradient and material time derivative through Eq.(4) and Eq.(10). Therefore, according to Eq. (4), the left-hand side of Eq. (11) becomes:

$$h \int_{\Omega^R} \left\{ \left[\mathbf{C} : \nabla^R \mathbf{u}^R \mathbf{J}_{\Psi}^{-1} \right] \nabla^R \delta \mathbf{u}^R \mathbf{J}_{\Psi}^{-1} \right\} \bar{J}_{\Omega} d\Omega^R - h \int_{\Omega^R} \left\{ \mathbf{f} \delta \mathbf{u}^R \right\} \bar{J}_{\Omega} d\Omega^R + h \int_{\partial\Omega_p^R} \left\{ \mathbf{p} \delta \mathbf{u}^R \right\} \bar{J}_S dS^R \quad (13)$$

Similarly, using Eq. (10), the right-hand side of Eq. (11) assumes the following form:

$$-h \int_{\Omega^R} \left\{ \rho \left[\ddot{\mathbf{u}}^R - 2\nabla^R \dot{\mathbf{u}}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R - \nabla^R \mathbf{u}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \ddot{\mathbf{X}}^R + \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \nabla^R \left[\nabla^R \mathbf{u}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \right] \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R + \nabla^R \mathbf{u}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \nabla^R \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \mathbf{J}_\Psi^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}}^R \right] \delta \mathbf{u}^R \right\} \bar{J}_\Omega d\Omega^R \quad (14)$$

In Eqs. (13) and (14), \mathbf{u}^R and $\delta \mathbf{u}^R$ denotes the displacement and virtual displacements fields conforming to Eqs. (12) and expressed in the referential domain R_χ . In addition, Ω^R is the area of the body in the referential domain, $\partial\Omega_p^R$ is the boundary region affected by external tractions in the referential configuration, while \bar{J}_Ω and \bar{J}_ζ represent the Jacobian related to the volume and area, respectively.

The governing equations of the moving mesh problem aim to smoothly deform the computational mesh consistently with the growth of internal defects while avoiding excessive distortions for finite elements. In the framework of moving mesh techniques, there are different ways to express governing equations concerning the motion of the computational nodes, each of them identifies a smoothing (or rezoning) method. Among the different smoothing methods available in the literature, the one adopted in the proposed method is the Laplacian (or Poisson) smoothing. The Laplacian smoothing consists of solving the following partial differential equation within the computational domain:

$$\nabla^M \cdot \nabla^M \mathbf{x} = 0 \quad (15)$$

where, $\mathbf{x} = [x_1 \ x_2]$ is the vector position identifying the spatial coordinates of mesh nodes in the current configuration (*i.e.*, at $t = \bar{t}$).

Solving the Laplace smoothing of Eq. (15) requires a suitable set of boundary conditions. To this end, one introduces the nodal mesh displacement vector function, defined as $\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{X}$, in which the material coordinates \mathbf{X} are intended representative of the initial position of the mesh nodes. Twofold conditions are employed to adapt the computational mesh to the geometry evolutions because of dynamically growing crack: The first condition requires that the mesh node of the crack tip moves along the direction of propagation (\mathbf{n}_c) at a speed equal to the crack tip velocity \dot{a} . The second condition imposes no mesh displacements along the external boundary of the body. Hence, the boundary conditions for the moving mesh problem can be summarized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{\mathbf{x}}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_c &= \dot{a} \quad \text{at } O_c \\ \bar{\mathbf{x}} &= 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

in which $\dot{\bar{\mathbf{x}}}$ represents the time derivative of nodal mesh displacement vector function. Noting that both \mathbf{n}_c and \dot{a} can be defined using any fracture criteria defined in the framework of fracture mechanics. For instance, concerning the propagation direction \mathbf{n}_c , one can adopt the maximum hoop stress criterion developed by Erdogan and Sin [38] or the maximum energy release rate criterion proposed by Hussain et al. [39]. Regarding the crack tip velocity \dot{a} , suitable expressions consistent with experimental findings are those proposed by Freund in [1] or Kanninen and Popelar in [43].

Defining the following sets of vector positions in the varied configuration and the related weighting functions:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{x} &= \left\{ \mathbf{x} \in H^1(\Omega) \mid \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{X} \text{ on } \partial\Omega \right\} \\ \delta\mathbf{x} &= \left\{ \delta\mathbf{x} \in H^1(\Omega) \mid \delta\mathbf{x} = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

The weak form of Laplacian smoothing described by Eq.(15) assumes the following form:

$$\int_{\Omega_R} \left[\nabla^R(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{J}_{\Psi}^{-1} \right] \left[\nabla^R(\delta\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{J}_{\Psi}^{-1} \right] \bar{J}_{\Omega} d\Omega_R = 0 \quad (18)$$

To account for the boundary conditions defined by Eqs.(16), the Lagrangian Multipliers Method (LMM) is employed. Therefore, Eq.(18) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}\int_{\Omega_R} \left[\nabla^R(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{J}_{\Psi}^{-1} \right] \cdot \left[\nabla^R(\delta\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{J}_{\Psi}^{-1} \right] \bar{J}_{\Omega} d\Omega_R + \\ + \int_{\Gamma_c} \left[\delta\lambda (\dot{\bar{\mathbf{x}}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_c - \dot{a}) + \lambda \delta(\dot{\bar{\mathbf{x}}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_c) \right] d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_R} \left[\delta(\lambda) \bar{\mathbf{x}} + \lambda \delta(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) \right] \bar{J}_{\Gamma} d\Gamma_R = 0\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

where, λ is the LMM vector.

2.3 Dynamic fracture mechanics

2.3.1 *DSIFs computing: the interaction integral method in moving coordinates*

The interaction integral method, also known as *M*-integral, is probably the most effective approach in computational fracture mechanics for extracting fracture variables at the crack front, such as Stress Intensity Factors (SIFs) and T-stress. The *M*-integral expression derives from the *J*-integral applied to a superimposed state, which results from the combination of displacement, stress, and strain fields of the problem under investigation (whose SIFs worth be computed) and the ones relative to an auxiliary solution with known SIFs.

In dynamic fracture mechanics, the dynamic form of the *M*-integral is used to evaluate the Dynamic Stress Intensity Factors (DSIFs), which are fundamental parameters for defining crack onset conditions, the direction of propagation, and crack tip velocity.

To derive the dynamic *M*-integral expression, let us consider the analytical form of the dynamic *J*-integral, defined as follows [4, 44, 45] (Fig. 3):

$$J = \lim_{S_0 \rightarrow 0} \int_{S_0} \left[(W + K) \delta_{ij} - \sigma_{ij} u_{j,1} \right] n_i dS \quad \text{with } i, j = 1, 2 \quad (20)$$

where, S_0 is an arbitrary vanishingly small contour surrounding the crack tip, whose the unit outward normal vector is n_i , and δ_{ij} the Kronecker delta. Further, W and K are the strain energy density and the kinematic energy density, respectively defined as:

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}; \quad K = \frac{1}{2} \rho \dot{u}_j \dot{u}_j \quad (21)$$

ρ and \dot{u}_j being the mass density and velocity field, respectively.

It is generally known that Eq. (20) is not suitable for computing Dynamic Stress Intensity Factors (DSIFs) because of the difficulty of evaluating stress and strain fields along a vanishing contour surrounding the crack tip. For this reason, the curvilinear integral in Eq.(20) is usually converted into an Equivalent Domain Integral (EDI) form [46].

Fig. 3. The J -integral paths S_0 and S , the Equivalent Domain Integral (EDI), and a schematic representation of the arbitrary function $q(x_1^c, x_2^c)$.

To this end, let's define a closed path $S = S_1 + S_+ + S_- + S_0$, where S_1 is another closed contour (larger than S_0), and $[S_+, S_-]$ are crack face paths connecting S_0 and S_1 extremities (see Fig. 3). Afterward, by assuming a weighting function $q(x_1^c, x_2^c)$, equal to the unity on S_0 and zero on S_1 , under the hypothesis of absence of body forces and crack-face tractions on $[S_+, S_-]$, and accounting for Eqs. (21), Eq. (20) can be equivalently written as follows:

$$J = \lim_{S_0 \rightarrow 0} \oint_S \left[\sigma_{ij} u_{j,1} - \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} + \rho \dot{u}_j \dot{u}_j) \delta_{li} \right] m_i q dS \quad \text{with } i, j = 1, 2 \quad (22)$$

where, m_i is the outward normal on S (note that, $m_i = -n_i$ on S_0). By applying the divergence theorem to Eq. (22), considering that the limit $S_0 \rightarrow 0$ leads to $A_0 \rightarrow 0$, one achieves the following expression:

$$J = \int_A \left\{ \left[\sigma_{ij} u_{i,1} - \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} + \rho \dot{u}_j \dot{u}_j) \delta_{li} \right] q_{,i} + \left[(\sigma_{ij} u_{i,1})_{,i} - \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} + \rho \dot{u}_j \dot{u}_j)_{,1} \right] q \right\} dA \quad \text{with } i, j = 1, 2 \quad (23)$$

In addition, by noting that $(\sigma_{ij} u_{j,1})_{,i} = \sigma_{ij,i} u_{j,1} + \sigma_{ij} u_{i,j,1} = \sigma_{ij,i} u_{j,1} + \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij,1}$, $\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij,1} = C_{ijhk} \varepsilon_{hk} \varepsilon_{ij,1} = \varepsilon_{hk} \sigma_{hk,1} = \varepsilon_{ij} \sigma_{ij,1}$, and considering that $\sigma_{ij,j} = \rho \ddot{u}_i$, Eq. (23) simplifies as follows:

$$J = \int_A \left\{ \left[\sigma_{ij} u_{i,1} - \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} + \rho \dot{u}_j \dot{u}_j) \delta_{li} \right] q_{,i} + \rho [\ddot{u}_i u_{j,1} - \dot{u}_{j,1} \dot{u}_j] q \right\} dA \quad \text{with } i, j = 1, 2 \quad (24)$$

which is the EDI form of the dynamic J -integral.

The M -integral expression results by applying Eq. (24) to the superimposed state "act+aux", thus achieving $J^{act+aux} = J^{act} + J^{aux} + M$, in which M is the mutual term equal to:

$$M = \int_A \left[(\sigma_{ij}^{act} u_{j,1}^{aux} + \sigma_{ij}^{aux} u_{j,1}^{act}) - (\sigma_{ij}^{act} \varepsilon_{ij}^{aux} + \rho \dot{u}_j^{act} \dot{u}_j^{aux}) \delta_{li} \right] q_{,i} dA + \int_A \left[\rho (\ddot{u}_j^{act} u_{j,1}^{aux} + \ddot{u}_j^{aux} u_{j,1}^{act}) - \rho (\dot{u}_{j,1}^{act} \dot{u}_j^{aux} + \dot{u}_{j,1}^{aux} \dot{u}_j^{act}) \right] q dA \quad (25)$$

Usually, the auxiliary fields used for analyzing fracture problems under quasi-static conditions have also been employed for dynamic fracture investigations (see, for instance, [47-50]). In particular, the auxiliary fields used in quasi-static fracture analyses are consistent with displacement, strain, and stress fields relative to Williams' asymptotic solution [51] of a straight crack in an infinite plate under remote loadings (see Appendix A). Although these solutions have been developed under quasi-static conditions, their applicability to dynamic fracture is valid because of the similarity between the asymptotic fields of dynamic and quasi-static problems, as highlighted in [52, 53]. Using Williams' asymptotic solutions determines that the auxiliary velocity and acceleration fields are zero (namely $\dot{u}_i^{aux} = 0$ and $\ddot{u}_i^{aux} = 0$), thus achieving the following simplified expression for the M -integral:

$$M = \int_A \left[\left(\sigma_{ij}^{act} u_{j,1}^{aux} + \sigma_{ij}^{aux} u_{j,1}^{act} \right) - \left(\sigma_{ij}^{act} \varepsilon_{ij}^{aux} \right) \delta_{li} \right] q_{,i} dA + \int_A \rho \left(\ddot{u}_j^{act} u_{j,1}^{aux} \right) q dA \quad (26)$$

which is similar to that reported in [50, 54]. However, the effect of non-zero crack propagation velocity on the M -integral can be properly accounted for (see, for instance, [55, 56]) by assuming as auxiliary fields the analytic solutions concerning a steady state propagating crack problem derived by Rise [57] (Appendix A). These solutions refer to an advancing crack coordinate system (x_1^c, x_2^c) , centered at the crack tip, that moves at constant velocity \dot{a} with respect to a fixed coordinate system (X_1^c, X_2^c) , as shown in Fig. 4. In particular, these two coordinate systems are related by the following relationships:

$$\begin{cases} x_1^c = X_1^c - a(t) \\ x_2^c = X_2^c \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

being $a(t)$ the current crack propagation distance from the origin of the fixed coordinate system. Starring from the first of Eqs. (27), the material time derivative in the moving coordinate of the displacement component u_i along the x_1^c axis can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{du_i}{dt} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1^c} \frac{\partial a}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} - \dot{a} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1^c} \quad (28)$$

where \dot{a} is the crack tip velocity.

Fig. 4. Auxiliary moving crack tip coordinate system according to Rise's analytical solution reported in [57]

Under steady-state condition, the first term in Eq. (28) is zero, so one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{u}_i &= -\dot{a}u_{i,1} \\ \dot{u}_{i,1} &= -\dot{a}u_{i,11}\end{aligned}\quad (29)$$

Eqs. (29) can be used to express auxiliary velocity fields in Eq. (25). However, as denoted by Freund and Clifton [58] and also by Nielson [59], the analytic solutions under steady-state propagating crack conditions proposed by Rise are also valid when the propagation velocity varies with time. According to such a condition, by exploiting the first relationship of Eq. (29), one derives the material time acceleration as follows:

$$\ddot{u}_i = -\frac{\partial \dot{a}}{\partial t} u_{i,1} - \dot{a} \dot{u}_{i,1} = -\ddot{a} u_{i,1} - \dot{a} \dot{u}_{i,1} \quad (30)$$

Eqs. (29)-(30) can be used to express the auxiliary velocity and acceleration fields in Eq.(25).

The ALE formulation of the M -integral results by projecting the actual terms in Eq. (25) concerning displacements, stress, and stress fields into the referential system of coordinates (R_χ), thus achieving:

$$\begin{aligned}M &= \int_{A_R} \left[\left(C_{ijkl} u_{i,h}^R (\chi_h)_{,n}^M (X_n)_j^C u_{j,1}^{aux} + \sigma_{ij}^{aux} u_{i,h}^R (\chi_h)_{,n}^M (X_n)_{,1}^C \right) \right] \left[q_{,h} (\chi_h)_{,n}^M (X_n)_i^C \right] \bar{J}_A dA_R + \\ &- \int_{A_R} \left[\left(C_{ijkl} u_{i,h}^R (\chi_h)_{,n}^M (X_n)_j^C \varepsilon_{ij}^{aux} + \rho \Gamma_i (\dot{u}_i^M) \dot{u}_j^{aux} \right) \delta_{li} \right] \left[q_{,h} (\chi_h)_{,n}^M (X_n)_i^C \right] \bar{J}_A dA_R \\ &+ \int_{A_R} \left[\rho \left(\Gamma_i (\ddot{u}_i^M) u_{j,1}^{aux} + \ddot{u}_j^{aux} u_{i,h}^R (\chi_h)_{,n}^M (X_n)_{,1}^C \right) \right] q \left[\Gamma_i (\Psi_i (\chi_i)) \right] \bar{J}_A dA_R \\ &- \int_{A_R} \left[\rho \left(\left(\dot{u}_i^R - u_{i,n}^R (\chi_h)_{,n}^M \dot{X}_i^\chi \right)_{,h}^R (\chi_h)_{,n}^M (X_n)_{,1}^C \dot{u}_j^{aux} + \dot{u}_{j,1}^{aux} \Gamma_i (\dot{u}_i^M) \right) \right] q \left[\Gamma_i (\Psi_i (\chi_i)) \right] \bar{J}_A dA_R\end{aligned}\quad (31)$$

where $(\cdot)_i^R = \partial(\cdot)/\partial\chi_i$, $(\cdot)_i^M = \partial(\cdot)/\partial X_i$, $(\cdot)_i^C = \partial(\cdot)/\partial X_i^C$, A_R is the domain area in the referential system, \bar{J}_A is the Jacobian of the transformation, and Γ is the mapping function between the referential frame and the crack tip system of coordinates.

Once that M -integral is evaluated through Eq. (31), according to the relationship between the J -integral and DSIFs for two-dimensional crack problems in the context of LEFM, the following expression is valid for the superimposed state:

$$M = \frac{2}{E'} \left[K_I^{act} K_I^{aux} f_d(\dot{a}) + K_{II}^{act} K_{II}^{aux} f_s(\dot{a}) \right] \quad (32)$$

where, $E' = E$ for plane stress and $E' = E/(1-\nu^2)$ for plane strain. Besides, $f_d(\dot{a}), f_s(\dot{a})$ are the universal functions, depending on the crack tip velocity \dot{a} , defined as follows:

$$f_i(\dot{a}) = \frac{1}{\kappa+1} \frac{4\alpha_i(1-\alpha_s^2)}{4\alpha_d\alpha_s - (1-\alpha_s^2)^2}, \quad \text{with } \alpha_d = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\dot{a}^2}{c_d^2}} \quad \text{and } \alpha_s = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\dot{a}^2}{c_s^2}} \quad (33)$$

In Eq. (33), κ is the Kolosov's constant, which is equal to $3-4\nu$ and $3-\nu/1+\nu$ for plane strain and plane stress conditions, respectively. Besides, $c_d = \sqrt{(\lambda+2\mu)/\rho}$ and $c_s = \sqrt{\mu/\rho}$ are the longitudinal and transversal wave speeds, respectively, which depend on the Lamé's constant (*i.e.*, λ and μ) and the mass density of the material (ρ).

The DSIFs are computed using two M -integral expressions, evaluated by combining the actual state with a pure mode I (aux-I) and a pure mode II (aux-II) auxiliary fields. This combination provides two M -integral equations, namely $M^{act,aux-I}$ and $M^{act,aux-II}$, which provide the following simplified expression of the actual DSIFs:

$$K_I^{act} = \frac{E'M^{act,aux-I}}{2f_d(\dot{a})K_I^{aux-I}} \quad (K_{II}^{aux-I} = 0); \quad K_{II}^{act} = \frac{E'M^{act,aux-II}}{2f_s(\dot{a})K_{II}^{aux-II}} \quad (K_I^{aux-II} = 0) \quad (34)$$

2.3.2 Fracture criteria

The dynamic failure of a quasi-brittle material occurs because of rapid crack propagation mechanisms that, once triggered, develop in an unstable fashion unless they are arrested. Reproducing such complex phenomena accurately through a numerical method requires proper fracture criteria for identifying crack onset conditions, the velocity as well as the propagation direction of the crack front, and, finally, crack arrest events.

As denoted by Grégoire et al. [32], the dynamic fracture mechanics of a quasi-brittle material before crack onset differs considerably from what occurs during the crack propagation phase. This consideration relies on the fact that different material toughness thresholds characterize the fracture behavior of the material before and suddenly after crack onset. Specifically, a dynamic crack initiation toughness (K_{Id}) identifies the limit threshold for crack onset. In contrast, dynamic crack growth (K_{ID}) and arrest (K_{IA}) toughness values are associated with crack propagation and arrest events. Further, it is worth noting that K_{ID} varies with crack tip velocity (*i.e.*, $K_{ID} = K_{ID}(\dot{a})$) as highlighted by many experimental tests performed on quasi-brittle materials during the last decades [1, 4].

In view of all that has been mentioned so far, it transpires that the crack initiation event must be analyzed separately from the crack propagation and arrest phenomena. Therefore, two distinct fracture functions must be defined to identify (*i*) crack initiation conditions and (*ii*) analyze crack propagation mechanisms.

The definition of suitable fracture functions for investigating dynamic fracture mechanics in quasi-brittle materials necessitates a fracture criterion to define the direction of crack propagation and an effective fracture variable representative of fracture conditions at the crack front. Concerning this aspect, the proposed method adopts the maximum hoop stress criterion developed by Erdogan and Sih [38]. According to such a criterion, the crack propagation angle regarding the crack tip system of coordinates assumes the following expression:

$$\theta^* = \theta^*(K_I, K_{II}) = \begin{cases} 2 \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{K_I}{4K_{II}} - \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\left(\frac{K_I}{K_{II}}\right)^2 + 8} \right) & \text{for } K_{II} > 0 \\ 2 \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{K_I}{4K_{II}} + \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\left(\frac{K_I}{K_{II}}\right)^2 + 8} \right) & \text{for } K_{II} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

where (K_I, K_{II}) are the DSIFs at the crack front, evaluated through the M -integral method (see Section 2.3.1).

Besides, the maximum hoop stress criterion provides an equivalent Stress Intensity Factors (K^*) for investigating the fracture conditions at crack front, defined as follows:

$$K^*(K_I, K_{II}, \theta^*) = K_I \cos^3\left(\frac{\theta^*}{2}\right) - 3K_{II} \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta^*}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\theta^*}{2}\right) \quad (36)$$

The fracture functions adopted in the present method for analyzing the fracture behavior of quasi-brittle materials are expressed using K^* , and the material toughnesses K_{Id} , $K_{ID}(\dot{a})$, and K_{IA}

The first fracture function, denoted as f_F^I , serves to identify crack initiation conditions and it is defined as follows:

$$f_F^I = \frac{K^*}{K_{Id}} - 1 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} f_F^I < 0 & \text{(no initiation)} \\ f_F^I = 0 & \text{(initiation)} \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

The second, named as f_F^P , aims at describing the kinematic of crack tip motion, thereby quantifying the velocity of the crack tip and, further, defining the conditions for crack arrest.

$$f_F^P = \frac{K^*}{K_{ID}} - 1 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} f_F^P = 0 & \& \dot{a} > 0 & \text{(propagation)} \\ f_F^P = 0 & \& \dot{a} = 0 & \text{(arrest)} \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

Nothing that the applicability of f_F^P requires a proper relationship describing the dependency between K_{ID} and crack tip velocity (\dot{a}). To this end, the proposed method employs the empirical equation defined by Kanninen and Popelar [43], defined as follows:

$$K_{ID}(\dot{a}) = \frac{K_{IA}}{1 - \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{V_L}\right)^m} \quad (39)$$

where, K_{IA} is the crack arrest toughness, V_L is the limiting crack velocity in the material, and m is a dimensionless shape factor.

Fig. 5 illustrates a schematic of the Kanninen and Popelar equation for different values of the m factor. As one can see, for low crack tip velocities, the dynamic growth toughness assumes a constant value slightly higher than K_{IA} . By contrast, it grows as \dot{a} increases, reaching an infinite value as it approaches V_L . In the particular case when $\dot{a} = 0$, it results $K_{ID}(\dot{a} = 0) = K_{IA}$ and crack arrest occur. Fig. 5 also shows that the value of the crack initiation toughness (K_{Id}) is higher than the crack arrest threshold (K_{IA}). This aspect denotes that the energy needed to trigger the crack propagation is generally higher than that needed for maintaining the propagation. This observation further justifies the necessity of two distinct fracture functions for investigating crack initiation and crack propagation fracture phenomena. Finally, it is worth noting that the analysis of the crack propagation phase stated by Eq. (38) represents a constrained optimization problem aimed at quantifying the crack tip velocity.

Fig. 5. A schematic of dynamic crack growth toughness curves

3 Implementation aspects

The weak form of the fundamental equation of solid mechanics (Eq. (14)) and that concerning the Laplacian smoothing technique governing the motion of the mesh nodes (Eq.(19)) are implemented in a FE code based on a Galerkin approximation. The use of an FE-based modeling approach implies that the geometry of the problem under investigation must be discretized in a sufficient number of finite elements (N^e). This condition determines that the displacement field (\mathbf{u}), the current nodal mesh position (\mathbf{x}), and Lagrangian multipliers ($\boldsymbol{\lambda}$) must be expressed as the products between nodal variables and isoparametric shape functions, as follows:

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathbf{N}_i^U \mathbf{u}_i^*; \quad \mathbf{x} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathbf{N}_i^{ALE} \mathbf{x}_i^*; \quad \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathbf{N}_i^\lambda \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i^* \quad (40)$$

where (\mathbf{N}_i^U , \mathbf{N}_i^{ALE} , \mathbf{N}_i^λ) are the matrices of interpolation functions and (\mathbf{u}_i^* , \mathbf{x}_i^* , $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i^*$) are the vector variables of the i -th node. By substituting Eqs. (40) in Eq. (14) and Eq. (19), one achieves the following system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} &= \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{r}\boldsymbol{\lambda} &= \mathbf{0} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

In the first relation, which refers to the solids mechanics problem, \mathbf{M} is the consistent mass matrix, \mathbf{K} is the stiffness matrix, and \mathbf{f} is the external load vector. The second relation deals with the Laplacian smoothing method, where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{r} are the ALE matrix and vector, respectively.

The system of equations described by Eqs. (41) is solved using an implicit time integration scheme based on a generalized- α method, implemented in a commercially available software, *i.e.*, Comsol Multi-physics [60]. Comsol Multi-physics possesses a flexible and practical environment that allows an easy implementation of the weak forms defined by Eq. (14) and Eq. (19). Besides, it offers the possibility of expanding basic functionalities through dedicated apps linking the Comsol environment with specialist software devoted to

design, mathematics, and programming. For the proposed model, the LiveLink MatLab app is used to link Comsol with MatLab, thus allowing the management of Comsol functions (e.g., solving and post-processing procedures) in an automatized manner through MatLab command lines. Specifically, a user-made script code is configured to execute automatically the steps involved in the propagation process.

Fig. 6 shows a flowchart diagram that illustrates the steps adopted by the proposed method for reproducing dynamic fracture mechanisms occurring in quasi-brittle materials. As one can see, except for some preliminary operations concerning the input of the geometry, material properties, and boundary conditions, the remaining steps are executed automatically by the script code.

The input geometry of the problem under investigation can generally be configured either using the geometric tools made available by the COMSOL library or through a pre-built geometry created by a dedicated drawing software. In both cases, the configured geometry must include an initial pre-crack, represented by a polyline departing from the external boundaries and developing up to an internal crack tip (Fig. 7-a).

The code starts operating on the input geometry by adding an extra node to the internal polyline close to the crack tip (Fig. 7-b). This preliminary step is necessary to ensure that the initial pre-crack preserves its initial configuration during the propagation phase. Indeed, the proposed method reproduces the crack advance by stretching the inner extremity of the polyline according to fracture mechanics prescriptions concerning propagation direction and crack tip velocity. However, this mechanism should occur without altering the initial configuration of the pre-crack. The addition of an extra node close to the crack tip subdivides the inner polyline into two portions. The first is the longest one that departs from the external boundary up to the extra node. This portion remains fixed during the propagation process. The second is a short segment that will be stretched during the propagation process, thus reproducing the crack growth.

Fig. 6. Flowchart of the propagation process

Fig. 7. Schematic sketches describing some steps involved in the propagation process configured by the proposed method: (a) Input geometry. (b) Forming stretching segment. (c) Propagation phase. (d) Geometry update occurring when $\theta_c > \text{Toll}(\theta_c)$.

Once the stretching segment is created, the code meshes the geometry and starts the analysis. For each time step, the model computes the Dynamic Stress Intensity Factors using the M -integral method, then evaluates a preliminary value for the kinking angle (through Eq. (35)), and finally assesses crack initiation conditions through the fracture function f_F^I defined by Eq.(37). When $f_F^I = 0$, the dynamic propagation takes place. From this point, the fracture process is entirely governed by the fracture function f_F^P (Eq.(38)). Hence, the mesh node of the crack tip advances at a velocity \dot{a} (evaluated by solving the constrained optimization problem defined through Eq. (38)) along the direction identified by the instantaneous value of propagation angle (Eq.(35)) (see Fig. 7-c).

During the motion of the crack tip mesh node, the finite elements around the crack tip region undergo distortions, which can negatively affect the accuracy of the numerical solution. To avoid loss of accuracy issues, the code executes a remeshing of the computational mesh when the finite elements distort considerably. In the present model, the mesh distortion is evaluated through the (nonnegative) first invariant of the isochoric Green–Lagrange strain relative to the computational mesh arrangement and defined as:

$$\gamma = \text{tr} \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}}{\det(\mathbf{F})} - \mathbf{I} \right) \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial \Phi^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}} \quad (42)$$

As a consequence, a threshold for the maximum mesh distortion must be set in the code ($\text{Toll}(\gamma)$). Therefore, a remeshing action occurs when $\gamma_{\text{Max}} > \text{Toll}(\gamma)$, being γ_{Max} the maximum value of γ evaluated among the finite elements of the computational mesh.

Besides checking the regularity of the computational mesh during the propagation, the code assesses the angle variation of the stretching segment regarding the initial pre-crack. This control needs for configuring proper reproduction of curved crack trajectories. Without loss of generality, a suitable threshold for the angle variation is $\text{Toll}(\theta_c) = 2^\circ$. When $\theta_c = \text{Toll}(\theta_c)$, the code stops the numerical simulation. Next, it updates the model's geometry by using the mesh configuration achieved at the time arrest of the analysis. The new

geometry serves as a novel starting point for the analysis. Therefore, the code inserts a novel extra node on the pre-crack, thus creating a new stretching segment. Then, the new geometry is re-meshed, and the code restarts the analysis. In particular, the analysis continues until either crack arrest conditions or overall collapse events occur. In the latter case, the analysis finishes, while in the former case, the analysis continues under the crack initiation criteria (Eq. (37)). If crack initiation conditions are satisfied, the propagation phase restarts.

4 Numerical results

This section reports numerical results to assess the proposed approach's reliability and accuracy in simulating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms occurring in quasi-brittle materials. Specifically, the investigation has examined three cases of study, which are well known for being among the most popular benchmark tests for checking the reliability of numerical methodologies devoted to simulating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle materials.

The first case, reported in Section 4.1, is introduced to validate the ALE formulation of the M -integral. It consists of an infinite plate with a semi-infinite mode-I crack whose analytical solutions are available in the literature. In particular, the analytical solutions provide the time evolution of the mode-I DSIF, relative to the cases of a stationary and a moving crack front (at constant velocity).

The second case, reported in Section 4.2, reproduces the experimental test developed by Kalthoff et al. [61] on a rectangular double cantilever beam made by Araldite-B. Specifically, Kalthoff et al. [61] have investigated the mode-I dynamic crack propagation process, evaluating the time histories of crack tip velocity and mode-I DSIF. Hence, this case provides prominent experimental data that allows assessing the overall reliability of the proposed method.

Finally, the last case reported in Section 4.3, is the well-known experiment performed by Kalthoff and Winkler [62] regarding a rectangular pre-cracked plate, with twofold horizontal notched, impacted by a projectile at a constant speed. The impact generated on the plate by the projectile induces mixed-mode crack propagation mechanisms that develop inside the plate, thus degrading its integrity. For this reason, this case represents a prominent test to assess the proposed method's ability to reproduce mixed-mode dynamic crack propagation phenomena in quasi-brittle materials.

Numerical models for reproducing such benchmark cases have been implemented using the same discretization strategy, comprising either plain stress or plain strain 9-node triangular-shaped finite elements arranged according to a Delaunay-type triangulation scheme. The behavior of materials is assumed to be linear elastic up to the failure. Numerical analyzes have been conducted using a standard PC with an Intel Core i7 920 running at 2.67 GHz with 16 Gb RAM.

4.1 Validation of the Arbitrarily Eulerian-Lagrangian formulation of the M -integral

Fig. 8 shows a schematic of a rectangular plate of length $L = 10$ m, height $2H = 4$ m, and thickness $B = 1$ m, with a horizontal pre-crack that develops along the mid-height from the left boundary up to the center of the plate.

Fig. 8. A rectangular plate with a horizontal notch under tension: a schematic of the geometry and boundary conditions

The Young's Modulus (E), the Poisson's ratio (ν), and mass density (ρ) are equal to $E = 210$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$, and $\rho = 8000$ kg/m³ respectively. Externally, the plate presents line constraints on the vertical boundaries that limit horizontal displacements. In addition, a uniform and distributed traction $\sigma_0 = 500$ MPa acts on the upper boundary.

The mode I DSIFs variation over time can be predicted using the analytical solutions developed by Freund [1] concerning an infinite plate with a semi-infinite crack under tension. In particular, such analytical solutions provide reasonable predictions of mode I DSIF until the stress waves generated by the traction σ_0 acting on the top boundary of the plate and reflected by the remaining ones reach the crack tip [29, 55]. More precisely, the interval of time of the validity of the analytical solutions has been estimated to be $0 < t < t_c = 3H/c_d$, where c_d is the dilatational wave speed, equal to $c_d = 5944.5$ m/s for the case under investigation.

Freund [1] has developed two sets of analytical solutions: the first set (**case 1**) provides the time evolution of the mode-I DSIFs for a stationary crack (*i.e.*, with no propagation). The second set (**case 2**) deals with a moving crack (*i.e.*, dynamically propagating) running at constant velocity. Of course, the latter case represents a significant test for assessing the ALE formulation of the M -integral proposed in the present paper.

According to these analytical solutions, the mode-I DSIF (*i.e.*, K_I) is zero until the stress waves reach the crack tip (*i.e.*, for $t < t_c$). Subsequently, for $t_c < t < 3t_c$, K_I can be evaluated using the following relationships:

$$K_I(0, t) = \frac{2\sigma_0}{1-\nu} \sqrt{\frac{c_d(t-t_c)(1-2\nu)}{\pi}} \quad (\text{case 1: Stationary crack}) \quad (43)$$

$$K_I(0, t) = \frac{2\sigma_0}{1-\nu} \sqrt{\frac{c_d(t-t_c)(1-2\nu)}{\pi}} \frac{1-\dot{a}/c_r}{1-\dot{a}/(2c_r)} \quad (\text{case 2: Moving crack}) \quad (44)$$

where \dot{a} is the crack tip velocity and c_r is the Rayleigh wave speed.

Besides the analytical solutions expressed by Eqs. (43)-(44), many numerical results are available in the literature. Among these, Chen et al. [55] have analyzed the fracture behavior of the plate using the Singular Edge-based Smoothed Finite Element Method (SE-FEM). Menouillard et al. [63] have used an XFEM approach improved by the crack tip enrichment methods. Such numerical methodologies evaluate K_I using the M -integral method, thus representing relevant references for assessing the accuracy of the proposed approach. In addition to the stationary and moving crack cases (*i.e.*, case 1 and case 2), both Chen et al. and Menouillard

et al. have examined a combined case (**case 3**) consisting of an initially stationary crack that starts moving at constant velocity for $t > 1.5 t_c$. Note that this combined case is valuable through the analytical solutions developed by Freund as well. Indeed, it is sufficient to use Eq.(43) up to $t = 1.5 t_c$ and then Eq.(44) for the sequel.

Simulating cases 2 and 3 through the proposed method has required some simplifications on the script code, introduced in Section 3, developed to manage the crack propagation phase. Specifically, conditions dictated by fracture functions f_F^I and f_F^P (see Eqs. (37)-(38)) have been replaced by switch statements, which simply impose that the crack front starts moving at a constant velocity $\dot{a} = 1500$ m/s for $t > t^*$. In particular, it is assumed that $t^* = 0$ and $t^* = t_c$, for case 2 and case 3, respectively. Besides, crack arrest events are excluded. This simplification provides the relevant benefit of focusing the attention exclusively on the moving mesh problem and DSIFs extraction.

Fig. 9 depicts the computational mesh adopted in numerical simulations (marked as Mesh M1). It comprises 432 triangular plane strain elements densely arranged around the crack tip region (where the minimum size of the element is $h = 0.1$ m) and is relatively coarser elsewhere. In particular, the stretching segment comprises four elements of variable length, as one can see from the zoomed view reported in Fig. 9.

In the numerical model, the finite element distortion tolerance is set equal to $\text{Toll.}(\gamma) = 1$. Besides, the analytical solution developed by Rise (see Appendix A) has been assumed as auxiliary fields in the M -integral method.

Fig. 10 compares the normalized mode-I DSIFs (expressed as $K_I / \sigma_0 \sqrt{H}$) as a function of normalized time (t/t_c) predicted through the proposed method with the analytical solution developed by Freund [1] and numerical results achieved by Chen et al. [55] and Menouillard et al. [63]. In particular, Fig. 10-a shows the results relative to the case of the stationary crack (case 1), in which moving mesh functionality does not work, while Fig. 10-b illustrates the results for the dynamically advancing crack at constant velocity $\dot{a} = 1500$ m/s (case 2). Finally, Fig. 10-c reports the data of combined fracture problem (case 3), in which an initial stationary crack starts moving at a constant velocity $\dot{a} = 1500$ m/s for $t > 1.5 t_c$.

The results denote that the proposed strategy is in good agreement with both analytical solutions and predictions provided by numerical approaches proposed by Chen et al. [55] and Menouillard et al. [63].

Fig. 9. A rectangular plate with a horizontal notch under tension: computational mesh adopted in numerical simulations.

Fig. 10. A rectangular plate with a horizontal notch under tension: A comparison in terms of normalized Mode-I DSIFs as a function of the normalized time between the proposed method, analytical solutions developed by Freund [1], and numerical predictions achieved by Chen et al. [55] and Menouillard et al. [63] (a) Case 1: stationary crack. (b) Case 2: moving crack starting from $t/t_c=0$ (c) Case 3: stationary crack up to $t/t_c=1$, and then moving crack for $t/t_c>1$. (d) Percentage error between the numerical predictions and analytical solution for case 2 and 3.

Regarding the fracture cases involving dynamically propagating cracks (*i.e.*, case 2 in Fig. 10-b and case 3 in Fig. 10-c), Fig. 10-d reports the percentage error between the numerical predictions and the analytical solutions proposed by Freund, defined as follows:

$$e(\%) = \frac{|K_I^{\text{analyt.}} - K_I^{\text{num.}}|}{K_I^{\text{analyt.}}} \quad (45)$$

In particular, the upper plot of Fig. 10-d examines the error variation concerning case 2, whereas the bottom graph shows the error relative to the case 3.

Fig. 10-d highlights that the proposed approach evaluates K_I somewhat correctly during the mesh motion, as denoted by the percentage variations, which are less than 10% in both cases and comparable with the predictions of Chen et al. [55] and Menouillard et al. [63]. These results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed method based on the use of M -integral in the context of the ALE formulation. However, it is worth noting that the curves of the relative errors achieved by the proposed method present an oscillatory behavior with peaks of divergence from the analytical solution. These peaks probably occur because the finite elements of the computational mesh have undergone relevant distortions. Indeed, any time there is a divergence peak, the numerical model updates the computational mesh (see the green points on the curves). A remeshing event restores mesh regularity, and numerical accuracy improves accordingly.

These results denote that the accuracy of the proposed strategy can be strictly dependent on the computational mesh arrangement and the finite element distortion tolerance (*i.e.*, $Toll. (\gamma)$) adopted in the numerical model. In order to examine these aspects in detail, two additional parametric analyses are developed. Since the scope of the additional parametric analyses is to check the effectiveness of the ALE formulation of the M -integral, numerical simulations are performed only concerning the fracture case of the dynamically propagation crack at a constant speed of $\dot{a} = 1500$ m/s (*i.e.*, case 2).

The first parametric study aims to investigate the influence of mesh discretization on the accuracy of the proposed method. To this end, further numerical simulations are developed using the computational meshes illustrated in Fig. 11, denoted as Mesh M2 and Mesh M3, respectively. Similar to the design strategy adopted for Mesh M1, both Mesh M2 and Mesh M3 are more refined in the region around the crack tip, rather than in the remaining part of the computational domain. Table 1 summarizes the statistics of the Mesh adopted. As one can see, Mesh M2 is the coarsest of the set, involving 175 triangular elements and 100 computational nodes. Conversely, Mesh M3 is the most refined, since it has 1113 triangular elements and 596 computational nodes. Such arrangements are representative of a wide range of possible computational meshes usable with the proposed approach.

Fig. 11. A schematic of the additional set of computational mesh discretizations defined for simulating the dynamic crack propagation fracture problem of rectangular plate with a horizontal notch under tension: (a) Mesh M2 and (b) Mesh M3

Table 1. Statistics of Mesh M1, M2, M3

Mesh	Number of DOFs	Triangular Elements			Stretching segment		
		Number of Elements	Maximum size (mm)	Minimum size (mm)	Number of Elements	Maximum size (mm)	Minimum size (mm)
M1	238	432	758,00	74,87	4	186,7	74,56
M2	100	175	1451,95	124,10	3	211,86	125,26
M3	596	1113	417,63	37,30	6	153,45	35,48

Fig. 12-a compares the normalized mode-I DIF (*i.e.*, $K_I / \sigma_0 \sqrt{H}$) as a function of the normalized time (t/t_c) for the mesh arrangements considered. The results highlight that the proposed strategy ensures acceptable levels of accuracy in extracting K_I during the mesh movement regardless of the mesh discretization. However, it is worth noting that the examined meshes involve different computational times to perform the simulation and a variable amount of total remeshing events needed to restore mesh regularity during crack propagation phase (Table 2). Examining these results, it transpires that Mesh M3 is the most computationally expensive. By contrast, the Mesh M2 is the most profitable for a preliminary evaluation of the problem. Mesh M1 represents the best compromise between numerical accuracy and computational efficiency.

Fig. 12. A rectangular plate with a horizontal notch under tension: Normalized mode-I DSIF versus normalized time. (a) Influence of mesh discretization. (b) Influence of finite element distortion tolerance $Toll.(\gamma)$.

Table 2. A rectangular plate with a horizontal notch under tension affected by a dynamically propagation crack at constant velocity: Computational Time and number of Remeshing Events between the mesh frames

Mesh	Computational Time (s)	Number of Remeshing Events
M1	53	11
M2	41	8
M3	98	16

The second parametric analysis examines the influence of the maximum threshold for finite elements distortion, *i.e.* $Toll.(\gamma)$ (see, Eq. (42)).

Specifically, the numerical simulation of the plate affected by a dynamically growing crack (case 2) is repeated by assuming different values of $Toll.(\gamma)$. It is expected that $Toll.(\gamma)$ represents a key variable for the efficiency of the proposed method because it implicitly influences the number of remeshing events occurring during the analysis.

Fig. 12-b depict the variability of the normalized mode-I DSIF as a function of normalized time for values of $Toll.(\gamma)$ equal to 0.5, 1, 2, and 3. As expected, the results denote that $Toll.(\gamma)$ considerably influences the reliability of the numerical solution. In particular, accurate numerical results are ensured by fixing $Toll.(\gamma)$ no more than 2. For $Toll.(\gamma) > 2$, the numerical results differ notably from the analytical solution. In particular, one observes relevant peaks of divergence from the analytical solution, probably because of the occurrence of relevant distortions in the finite elements of computational mesh. These peaks mark the occurrence of remeshing events. In fact, the accuracy of the numerical solution improves once a remeshing action occurs.

Table 3 reports statistics concerning computational time and the number of remeshing events. Here we can see that a reduction of $Toll.(\gamma)$ leads to a notable increment of the computational time and remeshing events. This trend is quite evident by comparing the results achieved by fixing $Toll.(\gamma) = 0.5$ and $Toll.(\gamma) = 3$. Hence, suitable values of the $Toll.(\gamma)$ parameter can be selected in the range $1 < Toll.(\gamma) < 2$, which ensures a good level of accuracy in DSIFs evaluation while avoiding excessive computational burdens. The advantage for such a range of values for $Toll.(\gamma)$ is also confirmed by observing the computational time and the number of remeshing events that occurred for $Toll.(\gamma) = 3$. This threshold value does not provide substantial benefits because the associated computational time is higher than that spent by setting $Toll.(\gamma)$ equal to 1 or 2. It seems possible that the larger computational time spent to perform the simulation occurs because of some convergence issues in the numerical solver. Probably, the numerical solver needed more iterative steps to find numerical convergence, thus spending more computational time. This difficulty is likely to be related to the excessive distortions undergone by the finite elements of computational mesh, which are also marked by the peaks of divergence from the analytical solution.

Table 3. A rectangular plate with a horizontal notch under tension affected by a dynamically propagation crack at constant velocity: Computational Time and number of Remeshing Events between the mesh frames

$Toll.(\gamma)$	Computational Time (s)	Number of Remeshing Events
0.5	72	16
1	53	11
2	45	9
3	63	9

4.2 Mode-I dynamic crack propagation fracture into an araldite-B rectangular double cantilever beam

Fig. 13-a shows a rectangular double cantilever beam of length $L = 321$ mm, height $H = 63.5$ mm, and thickness $B = 10$ mm. On the left side, the beam presents a horizontal pre-crack of length $a_0 = 83.8$ mm. In addition, the beam has two circular holes of diameter $d = 25$ mm, placed symmetrically regarding the crack plane. The holes are distant $e = 16$ mm and $b = 20$ mm from the left boundary and the crack plane, respectively. They serve as allocation for the mechanical gauges of an experimental machine for conducting mode-I fracture tests. The experimental machine produces two vertical and opposite forces that dilate the notch's surfaces, thus promoting a crack propagation mechanism that develops horizontally from left to right. On the right boundary, line constraints limit the horizontal displacement of the beam. The beam is made of araldite-B whose mechanical properties are summarized in Table 4.

Fig. 13-b shows the geometry and mesh discretization adopted for reproducing crack propagation mechanism through the proposed model. The mesh comprises 480 plane stress triangular elements. According to the results developed in Section 4.1, the mesh discretization is refined in the region around the crack tip (where the side of finite elements has an average length of $h = 3.50$ mm) while it is relatively coarser elsewhere. The stretching segment comprises five elements of variable size, as one can see from the zoomed view.

Fig. 13. An araldite-B rectangular double cantilever beam: (a) a schematic of the geometric configuration and boundary conditions. (b) computational mesh used in numerical simulations

Table 4. Mechanical properties of Araldite-B

Young's Module (E)	3660 MN/m ²
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.39
Density (ρ)	1172 kg/m ³
Dilatational wave speed (c_d)	1919.1 m/s
Shear wave speed (c_s)	1059.9 m/s
Rayleigh wave speed (c_r)	966.28 m/s
Static fracture toughness (K_{IC})	2.32 MPa m ^{1/2}
Arrest fracture toughness (K_{IA})	0.76 MPa m ^{1/2}
Dimensionless shape factor (m)	3.9

Kalthoff et al. [61] have investigated this beam experimentally, evaluating crack tip velocity and mode-I DSIF evolution over crack tip advancement. Such experimental results, especially those concerning the crack tip velocity, represent relevant benchmark data, which many authors have used to validate their numerical approaches devoted to simulating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle materials.

Among these, Ooi et al. [33] have reproduced the experimental results of Kalthoff et al. using an advanced numerical method based on the Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method (SBFEM) [33]. Shahani and Amini Fasakhodi [16] have used a traditional FE-based numerical model utilizing a remeshing algorithm to reproduce crack advancement. Koh et al. [35] have employed a numerical strategy somewhat similar to that proposed in the present paper for reproducing the evolution of the geometry because of advancing crack, which consists of a moving-grid finite element method based on the Eulerian-Lagrangian Description (ELD). Besides, they have adopted an integral form of the energy balance criterion, initially proposed by Freund in [64], to govern the crack-tip motion.

The proposed approach has been used to simulate the dynamic crack propagation process induced in the double cantilever beam by the experimental machine using a two-step analysis procedure, similar to what Ooi et al. [33] have done. More precisely, the numerical model performs an initial quasi-static analysis, in which the external loads are progressively incremented until crack initiation conditions occur. For the proposed approach, according to the fracture function defined in Section 3, this condition arises when $f_F^I=0$ (see Eq.(37)). Next, starting from the numerical solution associated with $f_F^I=0$, a second transient-type analysis is performed in which the dynamic crack propagation process is simulated while keeping the opening load constant.

Fig. 14-a compares the time history of the crack extension predicted by the proposed method with the experimental results of Kalthoff et al. [61] as well as the numerical predictions of Shahani and Amini Fasakhodi [16] and Koh et al. [35]. Fig. 14-b depicts the snapshots of the deformed configurations of the beam predicted by the proposed method at the points of time history curve marked by Roman numerals in Fig. 14-a. As one can see, the proposed method agrees reasonably well with both the experimental data and numerical results predicted by the other numerical approaches.

From the analysis of the deformed configurations of the beam reported in Fig. 14-b, it transpires that the refined mesh zone adopted around the crack tip region advances together with the crack front. Besides, during the crack advance, the boundaries of the crack faces behind the crack tip became coarse as far as the crack front moves away from them. This result denotes an interesting strength of the proposed method, which relies on the possibility of using fine discretization only around the crack tip region (*i.e.*, only where it is necessary) since the refined zone evolves during the numerical simulation. Furthermore, such a feature highlights that the proposed method has a wide range of applicability. Indeed, it can be efficiently adopted for simulating dynamic crack propagation processes occurring in geometric domains of both small and large sizes with reduced computational honors.

Comparison results between the proposed method, the experimental data, and other numerical predictions are also conducted regarding the time histories of the crack tip velocity (Fig. 15) and mode-I DSIF (Fig. 16).

Fig. 14. An araldite-B rectangular double cantilever beam: (a) A comparison in terms of time history of the crack extension between the proposed method, the experimental data achieved by Kalthoff et al. [61], and numerical predictions of Koh et al. [35] and Shahani and Fasakhodi [16] (b) snapshots of the deformed configurations of the beam predicted by the proposed method.

Fig. 15. An araldite-B rectangular double cantilever beam: (a) A comparison in terms of time history of crack tip velocity between the proposed method, the experimental data achieved by Kalthoff et al. [61], and numerical predictions of Koh et al. [35] and Shahani and Fasakhodi [16]

Fig. 16. An araldite-B rectangular double cantilever beam: Time history of the mode-I dynamic stress intensity factor

The results highlight that the proposed method provides good reliability regarding the kinematic of the fracture propagation process since the predicted crack tip velocity is approximately the same as that predicted by other numerical methods and close to that evaluated experimentally. The results of K_I (Fig. 16) confirm the excellent accuracy of the proposed method in extracting mode I DSIFs.

The present benchmark case has been assumed as a reference for developing an additional parametric study devoted to analyzing the influence of auxiliary fields typology adopted in the M -integral on the accuracy of the proposed method.

As reported in Section 2.3.1, using the M -integral for evaluating DSIFs requires the definition of auxiliary displacement, stress, and strain fields concerning an analytical solution of a fracture problem for which DSIFs are known. Yu and Kuna [45] have pointed out two choice options as auxiliary fields concerning dynamic fracture problems. The first option consists of using the displacement and stress fields relative to Williams' asymptotic solutions [51], traditionally adopted in numerical simulations of crack propagation processes under quasi-static conditions (see Section A1 in Appendix A). Alternatively, one can adopt the analytical solutions for an advancing crack at constant velocity derived by Rise [57] (see Section A2 in Appendix A). Most of the studies reported in the literature have investigated dynamic crack propagation problems through the M -integral method adopting Williams' asymptotic solutions. However, such solutions do not account for dynamic effects.

Conversely, the analytical solutions proposed by Rise have been rarely adopted. To the authors' knowledge, only two studies (*i.e.*, [55] and [56]) have attempted to use the refined solutions proposed by Rise to simulate dynamic crack propagation processes in quasi-brittle materials. Moreover, a systematic understanding on the best auxiliary fields for the M -integral to accurately reproduce dynamic propagation processes is still lacking.

Therefore, to identify the best option between the auxiliary analytical solutions available in the literature, the numerical simulation of the double cantilever beam has been developed assuming the following three auxiliary fields to use in the context of the M -integral method:

- **Aux. fields 1:** Rise' asymptotic solutions under the hypothesis of non-uniform crack tip velocity.
- **Aux. fields 2:** Rise' asymptotic solutions under the hypothesis of uniform crack tip velocity.
- **Aux. fields 3:** Williams' asymptotic solutions.

Fig. 17 illustrates the results concerning the time histories of the crack tip velocity (Fig. 17-a) and mode I DIFs (Fig. 17-b). The time histories achieved by assuming the different auxiliary fields are somewhat comparable. Indeed, the numerical model predicts the same dynamic fracture behavior regarding crack tip velocity and mode I DSIFs evolution. There are several likely explanations for these results. First, analytical solutions developed by Rise tend to those developed by Williams for limited crack tip velocities; Second, both the analytical solutions present a singularity for the stress field, which limits the differences in case of high crack tip rates.

Although the considered auxiliary fields lead to similar results, there are differences in numerical implementation. Of course, using Williams' asymptotic solutions as auxiliary fields implicates that the auxiliary field's velocity is zero. This circumstance simplifies the kinematic description of the auxiliary displacement fields. More interestingly, the M -integral expression reduces notably since many terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (25) vanish. Therefore, based on the attained results and discussion, it is possible conclude that the best option for the auxiliary fields in the M -integral method can be Williams' asymptotic solution.

Fig. 17. An araldite-B rectangular double cantilever beam: a parametric study in terms of the auxiliary field adopted in the M -integral method. Aux. fields 1: Rise' asymptotic solutions under the hypothesis of non-uniform crack tip velocity; Aux. fields 2: Rise' asymptotic solutions under the hypothesis of uniform crack tip velocity; Aux. fields 3: Williams' asymptotic solutions.

4.3 A mixed-mode crack propagation problem: the Kalthoff-Winkler impact test

This section aims to assess the proposed method's ability to simulate mixed-mode dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle materials. The validation is conducted regarding the experiment developed by Kalthoff and Winkler [62], depicted Fig. 18-a. Kalthoff and Winkler have examined the fracture behavior of a pre-cracked rectangular plate impacted by a projectile. The plate has a width $L = 100$ mm, height $H = 200$ mm, and thickness $B = 1$ mm. Besides, it presents two horizontal notches of length $a = 50$ mm, placed symmetrically regarding the mid-height of the plate. In particular, the notches are distant reciprocally of a length $H_a = 50$ mm. The Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, and mass density are equal to $E = 190$ MPa, $\nu = 0.3$, and $\rho = 800$ kg/m³, respectively. Besides, the dynamic crack initiation toughness is equal to $K_{Ia} = 68$ MPa m^{1/2}.

The projectile impacts the plate on the left boundary between the two horizontal notches. The impact produces a simultaneous advancement of both crack fronts. In particular, Kalthoff and Winkler have reported that the crack trajectories of crack fronts are symmetric regarding the middle plane of the plate, inclined about $\alpha = 70^\circ$ regarding the horizontal.

Because of the symmetry of both the geometry and boundary conditions, and the crack trajectories (as emerged by experimental observations), only half of the plate geometry is implemented in the numerical model.

Fig. 18. The Kalthoff-Winkler impact test: (a) experimental scheme (b) a depiction of the geometry and boundary conditions inputted in the numerical model (c) numerical mesh adopted in numerical simulations

Specifically, only the upper part of the plate is considered by assuming as boundaries conditions those depicted in Fig. 18-b. Besides, a constant velocity of $v_0 = 16.5$ m/s is imposed on the boundary part between the horizontal notches to reproduce the effect induced by the projectile's impact.

Many researchers have used the Kalthoff and Winkler experimental test results as a benchmark to validate their numerical methods' ability to reproduce mixed-mode dynamic crack propagation phenomena. Belytschko and Tabbara [11] have adopted a meshless approach based on the element-free Galerkin method. Ooi et al. [33] have used the scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM). Yan et al. [65] have employed a Continuous-Discontinuous Cellular Automaton (CDCA) method. Noting that, all these authors assumed that crack propagates inside the plate at a constant velocity equal to $\dot{a}=0.15 c_s$ (where $c_s = 3100.9$ m/s represents the shear wave speed of the material) once that crack onset conditions are satisfied.

The geometry domain has been discretized using the computational mesh depicted in Fig. 18-c. It consists of 427 plain strain triangular elements arranged finely around the crack tip region and coarser elsewhere. In particular, the element size around the crack tip region, measured through the representative element length (h), varies between $1.10 \text{ mm} < h < 1.40 \text{ mm}$, whereas the remaining triangular elements have a size between $1.03 \text{ mm} < h < 11.21 \text{ mm}$. The stretching segment comprises 2 elements of variable length, as one can note by observing the zoomed view reported in Fig. 18-c.

Fig. 19-a compares the crack trajectories achieved by the proposed method with experimental evidence and numerical results gained by the numerical procedures mentioned above. Fig. 19-b illustrates snapshots of the deformed configurations marked in Fig. 19-a by roman numerals. The results show that the proposed method reproduces a crack trajectory of almost 70° regarding the horizontal as observed in experimental results and reproduced by other numerical methodologies.

Fig. 19. The Kalthoff-Winkler impact test: a comparison in terms of crack trajectory between the proposed model, experimental evidence, and numerical data (*i.e.*, Belytschko and Tabbara [11], Fei et al.[65])

The snapshots in Fig. 19-b confirm that the propagation process simulated by the proposed approach implicates that the refined mesh zone around the crack tip region advances simultaneously to the crack front.

Fig. 20 shows the time histories of DSIFs (K_I , K_{II}). The proposed method agrees with the results of other numerical methodologies, thus confirming the reliability and effectiveness of the ALE formulation of the M -integral to extract DSIFs at the crack front also under mixed-mode fracture conditions.

Fig. 20. The Kalthoff-Winkler impact test: comparison of the time histories of the DSIFs between the proposed model and the predictions of other numerical methodologies (i.e., Belytschko and Tabbara [11], Ooi et al. [33] and, Yan et al. [65]) reported in the literature.

It is worth noting that several studies in the literature have investigated the Kalthoff and Winkler test without fixing the crack tip velocity equal to $\dot{a}=0.15 c_s$, but assuming it as a unknown variable of the fracture problem to be computed (i.e., like the benchmark case analyzed in Section 4.2). Perhaps the earlier study developed under this assumption was carried out by Belytschko et al. [29], which have simulated the plate's fracture behavior using the XFEM method. More recently, Rabckuz et al. [12] and Lee et al. [13] have reproduced the crack propagation mechanism affecting the plate using meshless approaches consistent with refined particle difference methods.

All these studies report comparable results in terms of crack trajectory and crack tip velocity. In particular, it was found that crack onset conditions occurred at almost $t=26.5$ s after the beginning of the analysis. Afterward, the crack tip velocity suddenly increases and oscillates within 1500 m/s and 2200 m/s during the propagation phase for 40 s. Finally, it progressively decreases, and the analysis stops around 78 s. In this context, the decrement of the crack tip velocity manifests because the crack front approaches the upper boundary of the plate.

A proper calibration of material toughness thresholds is mandatory to reproduce fracture behavior predicted by other authors. More precisely, it is essential to select suitable values for the dynamic crack

initiation and arrest toughness (*i.e.*, K_{ld} and K_{IA}), and the shape parameter m for adequately defining the dynamic crack growth toughness (Eq. (39)) to be used in the proposed numerical model.

The necessity for a novel value for the dynamic crack initiation toughness (K_{ld}) relies on the fact that the initial threshold $K_{ld} = 68 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ implies crack onset conditions occurring at $t' = 17 \text{ s}$. Such a circumstance emerges from Fig. 21-a, which reports the variation over the time of the equivalent Stress Intensity Factors (K^*) evaluated through a numerical simulation of the plate without considering crack propagation events. Besides, Fig. 21-a reveals that the equivalent Stress Intensity Factors (K^*) at $t'' = 26.5$ is equal to $K^* = 136.8 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$. Therefore, it is assumed $K_{ld} = 136.8 \text{ MPa mm}^{1/2}$ in the numerical model to ensure crack onset conditions like those predicted by other authors.

Regarding the shape parameter m , it is assumed without loss of generality $m=3$. Finally, the value of the crack arrest toughness (K_{IA}) has been selected through a parametric study in terms of different values for K_{IA} lower than K_{ld} . The best fit with the results proposed by other numerical approaches has been achieved with $K_{IA} = 54.7 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$.

Fig. 21-b compares the time history of the crack tip velocity predicted by the proposed method with numerical results reported in [12, 13, 29]. The results show that the proposed method predicts reasonably well the crack tip velocity achieved by other numerical approaches, thus confirming its effectiveness for reproducing mixed-mode dynamic crack propagation phenomena.

Fig. 21. The Kalthoff-Winkler impact test: (a) variation over the time of the equivalent Stress Intensity Factors K^* with no crack propagation mechanisms. (b) Time history of the crack tip velocity. Comparison between the present method and results gained by Belytschko et al. [29], Rabczuk et al. [12], and Lee et al. [13].

5 Conclusions

This work has presented an effective modeling strategy for simulating dynamic crack propagation mechanisms in quasi-brittle materials. The proposed approach enhances the capabilities of a standard FE code through the Moving Mesh (MM) technique for reproducing the evolutions of the geometry domain caused by the growth of internal cracks. In particular, the proposed method uses a Moving Mesh technique consistent with the Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation (ALE), which adopts proper smoothing techniques that properly relocate mesh nodes during mesh motion, thus avoiding excessive distortions for the finite elements of the computational mesh. This feature provides high flexibility to handle random growing cracks, as frequently occurs in the dynamic fracture processes of quasi-brittle materials. Besides, it ensures relevant computational savings and reduces the possibility of accuracy issues.

As a key novelty, the proposed method implements the ALE formulation of the interaction integral method (*i.e.*, *M*-integral) to extract Dynamic Stress Intensity Factors (DSIFs) at the crack front. It is worth noting that the accuracy of the *M*-integral for mesh-based methods strictly depends on the arrangement of the computational mesh in the region around the crack tip. Usually, fine and regular-arranged computational meshes are mandatory for ensuring accurate results. The ALE formulation of the *M*-integral permits using this strategy on deforming finite elements (whose regularity decreases during the mesh motion) without losing accuracy. Further, such a formulation permits extracting DSIFs simultaneously as the crack front advances, thus achieving smooth crack trajectories.

The validity of the proposed modeling approach has been assessed by analyzing three popular benchmark cases widely used by many authors to validate their numerical strategy devoted to simulating crack propagation processes in quasi-brittle materials. For each case, the results predicted by the proposed method are compared with analytical, experimental, and numerical data reported in the literature.

In addition, several parametric analyzes concerning mesh discretization, maximum distortion threshold for finite elements, and typology of auxiliary fields adopted in the *M*-integral method have been developed.

The results have denoted that the proposed method is in good agreement with analytical solutions, experimental findings, and numerical results achieved by other numerical methodologies. In particular, results concerning the time histories of DSIFs for all investigated cases have revealed the efficacy of the ALE formulation of the *M*-integral proposed in the present paper. Besides, the accordance with the experimental results concerning the velocity of the crack tip has highlighted the reliability of the proposed modeling strategy in reproducing the kinematic of dynamic propagation processes.

Parametric analyzes have revealed that the proposed method combines an acceptable level of accuracy in numerical predictions with excellent computational efficiency. Regarding the latter aspect, the proposed approach permits using smart mesh configurations, refined only around the crack tip region and somewhat coarser in the remaining parts of the computational domain. In particular, the operative steps of the proposed method provide the relevant benefits of moving the refined zone simultaneously with the crack front. This feature represents an undoable point of strength of the proposed method because it permits analyzing large and complex geometry domains with reduced computational burdens.

In conclusion, the proposed approach represents a valid strategy to reduce the weakness of standard FEM procedures, which extensively use remeshing actions to trace random growing cracks (as usually occurred in dynamic crack propagation process in quasi-brittle materials). Implementing the ALE formulation of the M-integral provides the advantages of using a robust and straightforward approach to reproduce articulated crack propagation mechanisms in complex geometries.

6 Credit authorship contribution statement

Arturo Pascuzzo: Conceptualization, Designed the methodology, Creation of models, Visualized the study, and prepared the original draft of the manuscript. **Fabrizio Greco:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Conceptualization, Methodology, Reviewed and edited the manuscript, and supervised the study. **Domenico Ammendolea:** Methodology, Data curation, Software, Performing numerical simulations. **Paolo Lonetti:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Reviewed and edited the manuscript, and supervised the study.

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8 References

- [1] L.B. Freund, Dynamic fracture mechanics, Cambridge university press 1998.
- [2] L. Wang, L. Yang, X. Dong, X. Jiang, Chapter Nine - Crack dynamics and fragmentation, in: L. Wang, L. Yang, X. Dong, X. Jiang (Eds.), Dynamics of Materials, Academic Press 2019, pp. 387-493.
- [3] R. Barretta, R. Luciano, J.R. Willis, On torsion of random composite beams, Composite Structures 132 (2015) 915-922.
- [4] T.L. Anderson, Fracture Mechanics: Fundamentals and Applications, Third Edition (3rd ed.) ed., CRC Press. 2005.
- [5] R. Barretta, L. Feo, R. Luciano, Some closed-form solutions of functionally graded beams undergoing nonuniform torsion, Composite Structures 123 (2015) 132-136.
- [6] C.A. Duarte, O.N. Hamzeh, T.J. Liszka, W.W. Tworzydło, A generalized finite element method for the simulation of three-dimensional dynamic crack propagation, Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering 190(15) (2001) 2227-2262.
- [7] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, U. De Maio, S. Rudykh, A. Pranno, Macro- and micro-instabilities in incompressible bioinspired composite materials with nacre-like microstructure, Composite Structures 269 (2021) 114004.
- [8] U. De Maio, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, P. Nevone Blasi, A. Pranno, An investigation about debonding mechanisms in FRP-strengthened RC structural elements by using a cohesive/volumetric modeling technique, Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics 117 (2022) 103199.
- [9] D. Gaetano, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, A. Pascuzzo, A. Skrame, Comparative finite element modelling approaches for the seismic vulnerability analysis of historical masonry structures: the case study of the Cathedral of Catanzaro (Italy), International Journal of Masonry Research and Innovation 1(1) (2022).
- [10] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, A. Pascuzzo, C. Ronchei, A detailed micro-model for brick masonry structures based on a diffuse cohesive-frictional interface fracture approach, Procedia Structural Integrity 25 (2020) 334-347.
- [11] T. BELYTSCHKO, M. TABBARA, DYNAMIC FRACTURE USING ELEMENT-FREE GALERKIN METHODS, 39(6) (1996) 923-938.

- [12] T. Rabczuk, J.-H. Song, T. Belytschko, Simulations of instability in dynamic fracture by the cracking particles method, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 76(6) (2009) 730-741.
- [13] S.-H. Lee, K.-H. Kim, Y.-C. Yoon, Particle difference method for dynamic crack propagation, *International Journal of Impact Engineering* 87 (2016) 132-145.
- [14] B.N. Rao, S. Rahman, A coupled meshless-finite element method for fracture analysis of cracks, *International Journal of Pressure Vessels and Piping* 78(9) (2001) 647-657.
- [15] S. Acierno, R. Barretta, R. Luciano, F. Marotti de Sciarra, P. Russo, Experimental evaluations and modeling of the tensile behavior of polypropylene/single-walled carbon nanotubes fibers, *Composite Structures* 174 (2017) 12-18.
- [16] A.R. Shahani, M.R. Amini Fasakhodi, Finite element analysis of dynamic crack propagation using remeshing technique, *Materials & Design* 30(4) (2009) 1032-1041.
- [17] T. Nishioka, S.N. Atluri, Numerical Modeling of Dynamic Crack Propagation in Finite Bodies, by Moving Singular Elements—Part 1: Formulation, *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 47(3) (1980) 570-576.
- [18] G. Yagawa, Y. Sakai, Y. Ando, ANALYSIS OF A RAPIDLY PROPAGATING CRACK USING FINITE ELEMENTS, (1977) 109-122.
- [19] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, A. Pranno, S. Rudykh, Mechanical behavior of bio-inspired nacre-like composites: A hybrid multiscale modeling approach, *Composite Structures* 233 (2020) 111625.
- [20] A. Pranno, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, P. Lonetti, R. Luciano, U. De Maio, Band gap tuning through microscopic instabilities of compressively loaded lightened nacre-like composite metamaterials, *Composite Structures* 282 (2022) 115032.
- [21] K. Hyun Moo, L. Hae Sung, J. Un Yong, An incremental formulation of the moving-grid finite element method for the prediction of dynamic crack propagation, *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 158(2) (1995) 295-309.
- [22] D.V. Swenson, A.R. Ingraffea, Modeling mixed-mode dynamic crack propagation using finite elements: Theory and applications, 3 (1988) 381.
- [23] A. Pascuzzo, A. Yudhanto, M. Alfano, G. Lubineau, On the effect of interfacial patterns on energy dissipation in plastically deforming adhesive bonded ductile sheets, *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 198 (2020) 31-40.
- [24] A. Pascuzzo, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, P. Lonetti, A. Pranno, C. Ronchei, Investigation of mesh dependency issues in the simulation of crack propagation in quasi-brittle materials by using a diffuse interface modeling approach.
- [25] U. De Maio, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, P. Nevone Blasi, S. Vantadori, A refined diffuse cohesive approach for the failure analysis in quasibrittle materials—part II: Application to plain and reinforced concrete structures, *Fatigue and Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures* 42(12) (2019) 2764-2781.
- [26] U. De Maio, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, P. Nevone Blasi, S. Vantadori, A refined diffuse cohesive approach for the failure analysis in quasibrittle materials—part I: Theoretical formulation and numerical calibration, *Fatigue and Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures* 43(2) (2020) 221-241.
- [27] U. De Maio, N. Fantuzzi, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, A. Pranno, Failure Analysis of Ultra High-Performance Fiber-Reinforced Concrete Structures Enhanced with Nanomaterials by Using a Diffuse Cohesive Interface Approach, 10(9) (2020) 1792.
- [28] F. Greco, D. Gaetano, L. Leonetti, P. Lonetti, A. Pascuzzo, Structural and seismic vulnerability assessment of the Santa Maria Assunta Cathedral in Catanzaro (Italy): classical and advanced approaches for the analysis of local and global failure mechanisms, *Frat. Integrita Strutr.* 16(60) (2022).
- [29] T. Belytschko, H. Chen, J. Xu, G. Zi, Dynamic crack propagation based on loss of hyperbolicity and a new discontinuous enrichment, 58(12) (2003) 1873-1905.
- [30] L. Wen, R. Tian, Improved XFEM: Accurate and robust dynamic crack growth simulation, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 308 (2016) 256-285.
- [31] T. Menouillard, T. Belytschko, Smoothed nodal forces for improved dynamic crack propagation modeling in XFEM, 84(1) (2010) 47-72.
- [32] D. Grégoire, H. Maigre, J. Réthoré, A. Combescure, Dynamic crack propagation under mixed-mode loading – Comparison between experiments and X-FEM simulations, *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 44(20) (2007) 6517-6534.
- [33] E.T. Ooi, M. Shi, C. Song, F. Tin-Loi, Z.J. Yang, Dynamic crack propagation simulation with scaled boundary polygon elements and automatic remeshing technique, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 106 (2013) 1-21.
- [34] J.P. Ponthot, T. Belytschko, Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation for element-free Galerkin method, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 152(1) (1998) 19-46.
- [35] H.-M. Koh, H.S.H. Lee, R.B. Haber, Dynamic crack propagation analysis using Eulerian-Lagrangian kinematic descriptions, 3 (1988) 141-155.
- [36] J. Donea, A. Huerta, *Finite Element Methods for Flow Problems*, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, The Atrium, Southern Gate, Chichester, West Sussex, England, 2003.
- [37] F. Greco, P. Lonetti, A. Pascuzzo, A moving mesh FE methodology for vehicle-bridge interaction modeling, *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures* 27(14) (2020) 1256-1268.
- [38] F. Erdogan, G.C. Sih, On the Crack Extension in Plates Under Plane Loading and Transverse Shear, *Journal of Basic Engineering* 85(4) (1963) 519-525.
- [39] M.A. Hussain, S.L. Pu, J. Underwood, Strain Energy Release Rate for a Crack Under Combined Mode I and Mode II, in: G.R. Irwin (Ed.), *ASTM International*, West Conshohocken, PA, 1974, pp. 2-28.
- [40] J.F. Yau, S.S. Wang, H.T. Corten, A Mixed-Mode Crack Analysis of Isotropic Solids Using Conservation Laws of Elasticity, *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 47(2) (1980) 335-341.
- [41] F. Greco, D. Ammendolea, P. Lonetti, A. Pascuzzo, Crack propagation under thermo-mechanical loadings based on moving mesh strategy, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 114 (2021) 103033.
- [42] D. Ammendolea, F. Greco, P. Lonetti, R. Luciano, A. Pascuzzo, Crack propagation modeling in functionally graded materials using Moving Mesh technique and interaction integral approach, *Composite Structures* 269 (2021) 114005.
- [43] M.F. Kanninen, C.L. Popelar, *Advanced fracture mechanics*, (1985).

- [44] B. Moran, C.F. Shih, Crack tip and associated domain integrals from momentum and energy balance, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 27(6) (1987) 615-642.
- [45] H. Yu, M. Kuna, Interaction integral method for computation of crack parameters K-T – A review, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 249 (2021) 107722.
- [46] B. Moran, C.F. Shih, A general treatment of crack tip contour integrals, *International Journal of Fracture* 35(4) (1987) 295-310.
- [47] K.R. Jayadevan, R. Narasimhan, T.S. Ramamurthy, B. Dattaguru, A numerical study of T-stress in dynamically loaded fracture specimens, *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 38(28) (2001) 4987-5005.
- [48] M. Imachi, S. Tanaka, T.Q. Bui, Mixed-mode dynamic stress intensity factors evaluation using ordinary state-based peridynamics, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 93 (2018) 97-104.
- [49] F. Yan, P.-Z. Pan, X.-T. Feng, S.-J. Li, The continuous-discontinuous cellular automaton method for elastodynamic crack problems, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 204 (2018) 482-496.
- [50] S. Jamshidi, N. Fallah, Extended finite volume method with enriched HPCK shape functions for dynamic crack propagation modeling, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 239 (2020) 107327.
- [51] M.L. Williams, On the Stress Distribution at the Base of a Stationary Crack, *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 24(1) (1956) 109-114.
- [52] V. Parameswaran, A. Shukla, Crack-tip stress fields for dynamic fracture in functionally gradient materials, *Mechanics of Materials* 31(9) (1999) 579-596.
- [53] Z. Wang, L. Ma, H. Yu, L. Wu, Dynamic stress intensity factors for homogeneous and non-homogeneous materials using the interaction integral method, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 128 (2014) 8-21.
- [54] J.-H. Kim, G.H. Paulino, T-stress, mixed-mode stress intensity factors, and crack initiation angles in functionally graded materials: a unified approach using the interaction integral method, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 192(11) (2003) 1463-1494.
- [55] H. Chen, Q. Wang, W. Zeng, G.R. Liu, J. Sun, L. He, T.Q. Bui, Dynamic brittle crack propagation modeling using singular edge-based smoothed finite element method with local mesh rezoning, *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids* 76 (2019) 208-223.
- [56] M. Imachi, S. Tanaka, T.Q. Bui, S. Oterkus, E. Oterkus, A computational approach based on ordinary state-based peridynamics with new transition bond for dynamic fracture analysis, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 206 (2019) 359-374.
- [57] J. Rice, *Mathematical analysis in the mechanics of fracture*, An Advanced Treatise, H. Liebowitz Ed., Vol. 2 (1979).
- [58] L. Freund, R. Clifton, On the uniqueness of elastodynamic solutions for running cracks, *Journal of Elasticity* 4 (1974) 293-299.
- [59] F. Nilsson, A note on the stress singularity at a non-uniformly moving crack tip, *Journal of Elasticity* 4 (1974) 73-75.
- [60] COMSOL, COMSOL Multiphysics® v. 5.4, Stockholm, Sweden, 2018.
- [61] J.F. Kalthoff, J. Beinert, S. Winkler, Measurements of dynamic stress intensity factors for fast running and arresting cracks in double-cantilever-beam specimens, (1977) 161-176.
- [62] J.F. Kalthoff, S. Winkler, Failure mode transition at high rates of shear loading, *Impact Loading and Dynamic Behavior of Materials* 1 (1987) 185-195.
- [63] T. Menouillard, J.-H. Song, Q. Duan, T. Belytschko, Time dependent crack tip enrichment for dynamic crack propagation, *International Journal of Fracture* 162 (2010) 33-49.
- [64] L.B. Freund, Crack propagation in an elastic solid subjected to general loading—III. Stress wave loading, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 21(2) (1973) 47-61.
- [65] F. Yan, W. Zhang, P.-Z. Pan, S.-J. Li, Dynamic crack propagation analysis combined the stable scheme and continuous-discontinuous cellular automaton, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 241 (2021) 107390.

9 Appendix A: Auxiliary fields adopted in M-integral computation

This section reports the auxiliary fields used in the interaction integral method described in Section 2.3.1. Specifically, there are two sets of auxiliary fields that can be appropriately adopted in dynamic fracture computations. The first set deals with Williams' asymptotic solutions for a crack under quasi-static conditions. The second set regards the analytic solutions developed by Rise concerning a steady-state propagation crack in an infinite medium under a remote loading.

9.1 A1. Williams' asymptotic solutions

The Williams' asymptotic solutions [51] are reported concerning the loading remote schemes inducing pure mode I and pure mode II fracture conditions:

Displacement fields:

$$\begin{cases} u_1^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{8\mu\pi} \sqrt{2\pi r} \left[(2\kappa-1) \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \\ u_2^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{8\mu\pi} \sqrt{2\pi r} \left[(2\kappa+1) \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode I)} \quad (A1)$$

$$\begin{cases} u_1^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{8\mu\pi} \sqrt{2\pi r} \left[(2\kappa+3) \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \\ u_2^{aux} = -\frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{8\mu\pi} \sqrt{2\pi r} \left[(2\kappa-3) \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) + \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode II)} \quad (A2)$$

Stress fields:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{11}^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[1 - \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \\ \sigma_{12}^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \\ \sigma_{22}^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[1 + \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode I)} \quad (A3)$$

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{11}^{aux} = -\frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[2 + \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \\ \sigma_{12}^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[1 - \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right] \\ \sigma_{22}^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode II)} \quad (A4)$$

In Eqs. (A1)-(A4), $[r, \theta]$ are polar coordinates in the crack tip coordinate system, μ denotes the shear modulus, and κ is the Kolosov's constant, which is equal to $3-4\nu$ and $3-\nu/1+\nu$ for plane strain and plane stress conditions, respectively.

9.2 A2. Rise's solutions

The analytic solutions developed by Rise [57] assumes the following form regarding pure mode I and pure mode II loading schemes:

Displacement fields:

$$\begin{cases} u_1^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[\sqrt{r_d} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{2\alpha_d\alpha_s}{(1+\alpha_s^2)} \sqrt{r_s} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ u_2^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[-\alpha_d \sqrt{r_d} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) + \frac{2\alpha_d}{(1+\alpha_s^2)} \sqrt{r_s} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode I)} \quad (A5)$$

$$\begin{cases} u_1^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2\alpha_s}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[2\sqrt{r_d} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - (1+\alpha_s^2) \sqrt{r_s} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ u_2^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2\alpha_s}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[2\alpha_d \sqrt{r_d} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\alpha_s} \sqrt{r_s} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode II)} \quad (A6)$$

Velocity fields:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u}_1^{aux} = -\dot{a} \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{r_d}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{2\alpha_d\alpha_s}{(1+\alpha_s^2)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_s}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ \dot{u}_2^{aux} = -\dot{a} \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{\alpha_d}{\sqrt{r_d}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{2\alpha_d}{(1+\alpha_s^2)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_s}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode I)} \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u}_1^{aux} = -\dot{a} \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[-\frac{2\alpha_s}{(1+\alpha_s^2)\sqrt{r_d}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_s}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ \dot{u}_2^{aux} = -\dot{a} \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\mu D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{2\alpha_d\alpha_s}{(1+\alpha_s^2)\sqrt{r_d}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_s}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode II)} \quad (\text{A8})$$

Stress fields:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{11}^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1+\alpha_s^2}{D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{1+2\alpha_d^2-\alpha_s^2}{\sqrt{r_d}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{4\alpha_d\alpha_s}{(1+\alpha_s^2)\sqrt{r_s}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ \sigma_{12}^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2\alpha_d(1+\alpha_s^2)}{D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{r_d}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_s}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ \sigma_{22}^{aux} = \frac{K_I^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1+\alpha_s^2}{D(\dot{a})} \left[-\frac{1+\alpha_s^2}{\sqrt{r_d}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) + \frac{4\alpha_d\alpha_s}{(1+\alpha_s^2)\sqrt{r_s}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode I)} \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{11}^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2\alpha_s}{D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{\alpha_s(\alpha_s^2-1-2\alpha_d^2)}{\sqrt{r_d}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) + \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\sqrt{r_s}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ \sigma_{12}^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2\alpha_d}{D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{2\alpha_d}{\sqrt{r_d}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{2\alpha_s\sqrt{r_s}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \\ \sigma_{22}^{aux} = \frac{K_{II}^{aux}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2\alpha_s}{D(\dot{a})} \left[\frac{1+\alpha_s^2}{\sqrt{r_d}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_d}{2}\right) - \frac{(1+\alpha_s^2)}{\sqrt{r_s}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_s}{2}\right) \right] \end{cases} \quad \text{(Mode II)} \quad (\text{A10})$$

In Eqs. (A5)-(A10), $\alpha_d = \sqrt{1-(\dot{a}/c_d)^2}$ and $\alpha_s = \sqrt{1-(\dot{a}/c_s)^2}$, being c_d and c_s the dilatational and shear wave speeds of the medium, respectively. Besides, $D(\dot{a}) = 4\alpha_d\alpha_s - (1+\alpha_s^2)^2$, and $r_d = \sqrt{x_1^2 + \alpha_d^2 x_2^2}$, $\theta_d = \tan^{-1}(\alpha_d x_2/x_1)$, $r_s = \sqrt{x_1^2 + \alpha_s^2 x_2^2}$, $\theta_s = \tan^{-1}(\alpha_s x_2/x_1)$, in which $[x_1, x_2]$ are the cartesian coordinates in the crack tip coordinate system.